

What is the effectiveness of population health management in improving health delivery, health outcomes, and reducing inequalities? A Rapid Review

Authors: Salina Khatoon¹, Alesha Wale¹, Claire Morgan¹, Helen Morgan¹, Hannah Shaw¹, Jacob Davies², Rhiannon Tudor Edwards², Libby Humphris³, Adrian Edwards³, Deborah Edwards³, Ruth Lewis^{4,5}

1 Public Health Wales Evidence Service, Cardiff, United Kingdom

2 Centre for Health Economics and Medicines Evaluation, Bangor University, United Kingdom

3 Health and Care Research Wales Evidence Centre, Cardiff University, United Kingdom

4 Health and Care Research Wales Evidence Centre, Bangor University, United Kingdom

5 Bangor Institute for Medical and Health Research, Bangor University, United Kingdom

Abstract: Population health management (PHM) is an approach that aims to improve health and reduce health inequalities by data-informed planning and delivery of proactive care. It uses linked datasets to identify local 'at risk' populations which are then targeted with personalised interventions that deliver proactive and proportionate care. The aim of this rapid review is to identify the effectiveness of PHM in improving healthcare delivery, health outcomes and reducing inequalities.

An abbreviated systematic review methodology was used to conduct this review in order to provide the available evidence in a timely manner whilst maintaining attention to bias. The review included studies published between 2018 and 2025. Three comparative studies evaluating the effectiveness of a PHM approach in improving health delivery, health outcomes, or reducing inequalities were identified. Four further studies evaluated the effectiveness of specific interventions targeting high risk groups and were developed using a PHM approach. Included studies were conducted in the USA and the UK.

Key findings and certainty of the evidence: The *prevention focused integrated care models* led to increased costs of secondary care per patient per year, and costs per user of secondary care and led to mixed findings for emergency admissions, with no significant differences in primary care utilisation and health-related quality of life. The *social determinants of health focused care model* led to reduced emergency department visits, hospital admissions and costs per patient and led to improved health-related quality of life. The *community-based programme designed to improve care coordination and address clinical and social determinants of health*, led to mixed findings in terms of costs and healthcare utilisation. The *food supplementation intervention* led to the successful provision of food supplementation, reduced emergency department visits and hospitalisations. The *person-centred smoking cessation intervention* led to increased quitline engagement, increased treatment engagement and increased abstinence. The *clinic-to-community, physical activity referral intervention* led to decreased body weight and systolic blood pressure. Those with hypertension were found to have decreased body weight, systolic and diastolic blood pressures. The revenue generated from the model was larger than the cost of scholarship provided to those in need of financial support. The *social determinants of health screening and referral process intervention* led to increased screening rates, social work referral and more patients accessing the FindHelp.org resources. Acceptability and satisfaction with both the models of care and interventions was generally high but integrated care models found no differences in patient perceptions of support.

While the evidence base was limited by a small number of low-quality studies, the findings may inform the development of PHM approach. Most PHM approaches were resource intensive, delivered across multiple care settings, involving multiple collaborating partners and a range of personnel to deliver the interventions, so complexity may impact feasibility and implementation of the interventions. PHM is a broad approach that can be implemented in various ways and at different levels of the healthcare system, depending on population needs and priorities. However, within the literature the impacts of the different PHM components are poorly reported, making it challenging to determine the effectiveness of PHM overall. There was a lack of high-quality evidence, particularly UK based. Further research is needed to draw firmer conclusions.

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Evidence Service

Report Contributors

Review Team

Salina Khatoon, Alesha Wale, Claire Morgan, Helen Morgan, Hannah Shaw (*Public Health Wales Evidence Service*)

Economic Considerations

Rhiannon Tudor Edwards and Jacob Davies (*Centre for Health Economics and Medicines Evaluation (CHEME), Bangor University*)

Methodological Advice

Ruth Lewis (*Health and Care Research Wales Evidence Centre, Bangor University*)

Evidence Centre Team

Adrian Edwards, Ruth Lewis, Alison Cooper, Deborah Edwards, Micaela Gal and Liz Doe involved in stakeholder engagement, review of report and editing.

Public Partner

Libby Humphris

Stakeholders

Faye Sheldon, Brian Laing, Robert Atenstaedt, Tan Aggarwal, Hannah Lloyd (*Betsi Cadwaladr University Health Board*)

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A Rapid Review

(Report number: RR0049, March 2026)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

What is a Rapid Review?

Rapid Reviews abbreviate or omit some components of the systematic review approach to generate the evidence to inform stakeholders promptly whilst maintaining attention to bias.

Who is this Rapid Review for?

The research question was submitted by Betsi Cadwaladr University Health Board (BCUHB) to inform its strategic direction for reducing health inequalities and prioritise those with the greatest health and wellbeing needs. It seeks to inform a whole systems approach to prevention and early intervention that the Health Board and their regional partners will adopt from 2026/27 onwards.

Background / Aim of Rapid Review

Population health management (PHM) is an approach that aims to improve health and reduce health inequalities by data-informed planning and delivery of proactive care. It uses linked datasets to identify local 'at risk' populations which are then targeted with personalised interventions that deliver proactive and proportionate care. The approach is gaining pace across parts of the UK and in Wales where many exemplary practices have been implemented, such as the work undertaken in the Cwm Taf Morgannwg area. BCUHB is exploring PHM approaches to improve health and wellbeing, and experiences of people living in North Wales and reduce inequalities. It is important to understand whether PHM approaches can improve these outcomes. The aim of this rapid review is to identify the effectiveness of PHM in improving healthcare delivery, health outcomes and reducing inequalities.

Results of the Rapid Review

Recency of the evidence base

- The review included evidence available until the end of September 2025. Included studies were published between 2018 and 2025.

Extent of the evidence base

- Three comparative studies evaluating the effectiveness of a PHM approach in improving health delivery, health outcomes, or reducing inequalities were identified. This included the implementation of prevention focused integrated care models (implemented across two NHS Vanguard sites), a social determinant of health (SDoH) focused care model, and a community-based programme designed to improve care coordination and address clinical and social determinants of health. Four further studies were identified that evaluated the effectiveness of specific interventions targeting high risk groups and were developed using a PHM approach, which included a SDoH screening and referral process using the electronic health record in primary care, food supplementation intervention, person-centred smoking cessation intervention, and clinic-to-community physical activity referral intervention.
- The seven studies included: One pilot randomised controlled trial; three non-randomised control studies, including one pilot; one cohort study; one repeated measures study and one uncontrolled before and after study.
- Included studies were conducted in the USA (n=6) and the UK (n=1).
- All studies were considered low quality with considerable methodological limitations.

Key findings and certainty of the evidence

- The **prevention focused integrated care models** led to increased costs of secondary care per patient per year, and costs per user of secondary care and led to mixed findings for emergency

admissions, with no significant differences in primary care utilisation and health-related quality of life using the EQ-5D 5 L index.

- The **social determinants of health focused care model** led to reduced emergency department visits, hospital admissions and costs per patient and led to improved health-related quality of life.
- The **community-based programme designed to improve care coordination and address clinical and social determinants of health**, led to mixed findings in terms of costs and healthcare utilisation varying by medical insurance payer.
- The **food supplementation intervention** led to the successful provision of food supplementation, reduced emergency department visits and hospitalisations.
- The **person-centred smoking cessation intervention** led to increased quitline engagement, increased treatment engagement and increased abstinence.
- The **clinic-to-community, physical activity referral intervention** led to decreased body weight and systolic blood pressure. Those with hypertension were found to have decreased body weight, systolic and diastolic blood pressures. The revenue generated from the model was larger than the cost of scholarship provided to those in need of financial support.
- The **social determinants of health screening and referral process intervention** led to increased screening rates, social work referral and more patients accessing the FindHelp.org resources.
- Acceptability and satisfaction with both the models of care and interventions was generally high but integrated care models found no differences in patient perceptions of support.

Policy and Practice Implications

- While the evidence base was limited by a small number of low-quality studies, the findings may inform the development of PHM approach.
- Most PHM approaches were resource intensive, delivered across multiple care settings, involving multiple collaborating partners and a range of personnel to deliver the interventions, so complexity may impact feasibility and implementation of the interventions.
- PHM is a broad approach that can be implemented in various ways and at different levels of the healthcare system, depending on population needs and priorities. However, within the literature the impacts of the different PHM components are poorly reported, making it challenging to determine the effectiveness of PHM overall. Policymakers and practitioners should take this into account when designing interventions using the PHM approach.

Research Implications and Evidence Gaps

- There was a lack of high-quality evidence, particularly UK based. Further research is needed to draw firmer conclusions.
- As the studies were aimed at specific population groups, and were primarily conducted in the USA, this may affect the transferability of the findings, particularly given differences in healthcare systems, patient demographics, and service availability.
- Robust evaluations of the effectiveness of PHM, and its components, should be integrated into development and implementation of PHM.

Economic considerations

- Additional expenditure on public health is more productive than additional National Health Service (NHS) expenditure in terms of quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) generated at the population-level. However, there is a paucity of economic evidence at the PHM-level.
- Economic evaluations of PHM should consider changes in healthcare resource use and associated costs of implementing PHM alongside measures of effectiveness. This is particularly pertinent given high levels of resource intensity required to implement PHM and the variability in PHM components identified by this review.
- Dependent on PHM design, economic evaluations may wish to consider different perspectives, time-horizons or discount rates to reflect and capture important differences in costs or outcomes as per National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guidance.

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Full Description
ACG	Adjusted Clinical Groups
ACSC	Ambulatory Care Sensitive Condition
BPA	Best Practice Advisory
BCUHB	Betsi Cadwaladr University Health Board
CI	Confidence Interval
CM	Care Managers
EHR	Electronic Health Record
ED	Emergency Department
EIMG® model	Exercise is Medicine Greenville model
HBS	Health Behaviour Specialists
HCP	Healthcare providers
HFHS	Henry Ford Health System
ITQL	Illinois Tobacco Quitline
IRRs	Incident Rate Ratios
JBI	Joanna Briggs Institute
J-CHiP	Johns Hopkins Community Health Partnership
NHS	National Health Service
NRT	Nicotine Replacement Therapy
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
PA	Physical Activity
PHM	Population Health Management
PMPY	Cost per member per year
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses
PROGRESS-PLUS	Place of residence; Race/ethnicity/culture/language; Occupation; Gender; Religion; Education; Socioeconomic status, and social capital-Personal characteristics associated with discrimination, features of relationships and time-dependent relationship.
QALYs	Quality-Adjusted Life years
RR	Rapid Review
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
SDoH	Social Determinants of Health
SDT	Self-Determination Theory
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
WHO	World Health Organization

1 BACKGROUND

1.1 Who is this review for?

This Rapid Review was conducted as part of the Health and Care Research Wales Evidence Centre Work Programme. The research question was provided by Betsi Cadwaladr University Health Board (BCUHB). This review is intended to support strategic planning and service design, particularly in relation to improving healthcare delivery, health outcomes and reducing inequalities. The review is relevant to a wide range of stakeholders, including commissioners of population health management (PHM), local authority teams, third sector organisations, and education and training providers. Researchers and policy makers may find the evidence useful in shaping regional and national strategies.

1.2 Background and purpose of this review

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), PHM is a data-driven, people-centred approach that aims to improve the health and wellbeing of a defined population, focussing on a preventative approach. By identifying subgroups with similar characteristics and needs, it enables healthcare providers to deliver targeted and tailored interventions. PHM emphasises the importance of addressing social determinants of health and psychosocial needs, ultimately aiming to reduce health inequalities and improve overall health outcomes (WHO, 2023). A recent scoping review by Van Ede et al (2023) further describes six components of successful implementation of PHM. These components include: an accountable regional organisation, a cross-domain business model, integrated data infrastructure, a co-designing workforce and community, population health data analysis, and emergent implementation strategies (Van Ede et al., 2023).

Cwm Taf Morgannwg University Health Board explain that PHM can improve population health by data-informed planning and delivery of proactive care to achieve maximum impact for the health and wellbeing of the population. Linked datasets are used to segment, stratify, and model the local “at risk” or “rising risk” cohorts that in turn are used to design, target and personalise interventions to deliver proactive care and proportionate universalism to reduce health inequalities (Cwm Taf Morgannwg University Health Board, no date). In addition, a PHM Task and Finish Group recently established by Welsh Government define PHM as “*an approach that improves population health by data-informed planning and delivery of proactive care to achieve maximum impact for the health and wellbeing of the population. Linked datasets are used to segment, stratify, and model the local “at risk” and “rising risk” cohorts that in turn are used to design, target and personalise interventions to deliver proactive care and proportionate universalism to reduce health inequalities*”.

The success of PHM programmes relies on accurate risk assessment, the effectiveness of the selected interventions, the fidelity of implementation delivery, and cost-efficiency (Lenus, 2021). Swarthout and Bishop (2017) suggest the term PHM is used to describe the infrastructure devoted to delivering interventions. This might include preventative services, care models that detect and intercede when early signs of health deterioration are identified, and community-based programmes that address specified determinants.

NHS England have implemented a PHM approach for more than three years to address health inequalities. A wide range of exemplary practices have been identified from this approach

including South Asian communities in East Milton Keynes being supported to better manage their diabetes (NHS England, no date). In Wales, a PHM unit was established in 2021, which provides leadership and guidance for implementation of PHM approaches across the Cwm Taf Morgannwg area. They have successfully linked primary and secondary care data and applied population segmentation and risk stratification models to better understand their population and their needs. This team have documented multiple successful case studies which have resulted in a positive impact in its targeted population groups by reducing emergency admissions in Bridgend East and reducing the burden of winter fuel poverty in the Taff Ely Primary Care Cluster (Cwm Taf Morgannwg University Health Board, no date).

Betsi Cadwaladr University Health Board (BCUHB) are investigating the feasibility of implementing PHM to reduce inequalities in access, experience and health outcomes, and to improve the health and wellbeing of the population of North Wales. Therefore, it is important to understand whether the PHM approach has the potential to create positive impacts for population groups considered at risk within their area.

A preliminary literature review identified a lack of existing reviews examining the effectiveness of PHM in reducing health inequalities. However, primary studies were identified that appeared to be relevant. The aim of this rapid review was to identify and synthesise the evidence for the effectiveness of PHM in improving healthcare delivery, health outcomes and reducing inequalities.

1.3 Identifying studies that assessed a PHM approach

PHM as an overall approach has been described and defined in the literature in different ways. However, as described above, PHM approaches can vary significantly, and the specific components which can be incorporated to constitute a PHM intervention is less well defined. Within the literature there appears to be a lack of consistency or clarity when defining PHM, with definitions often being broad or vague. A recent scoping review (Van Ede et al., 2023) described the complexity of implementing PHM strategies and outlined six components that we felt incorporated the main key aspects of PHM. For the purposes of this review, we have used the six components of PHM as described by Van Ede et al., (2023) to help simplify and define what a PHM approach or intervention is. These included:

- an accountable regional organisation;
- a cross-domain business model;
- an integrated data infrastructure;
- a co-designing workforce and community;
- population data analytics; and
- emergent implementation strategies.

While there is no expectation that every PHM or intervention developed using a PHM approach would incorporate all six components, they provide a clear understanding of what constitutes a PHM approach and aligns well with the recent definition developed the PHM Task and Finish Group established by Welsh Government (see section 1.2)

A comprehensive search was conducted to identify relevant papers; this is outlined in sections 6.2 and 7.1. A two-stage full text screening process was used to identify relevant studies. An initial screening of retrieved papers focused on identifying studies that specifically stated they had used a PHM approach and met the inclusion criteria outlined in the protocol (and Table 3). During this initial stage, 206 papers were screened at full text, with a total of 55 studies identified that mentioned using PHM. However, it was clear that the term PHM had been used

inconsistently, and not all of the 55 studies described a PHM approach as defined by Van Ede et al (2023) and the PHM Task and Finish Group established by Welsh Government. Therefore, it was necessary to implement an additional screening stage to ensure we had captured only interventions that were using a PHM approach.

Furthermore, when considering the components described by Van Ede et al., (2023) and the definition developed by the PHM Task and Finish Group, we identified that a collaborative approach was a common element across both definitions. This component encompasses using linked datasets, breaking down silos, and fostering collaboration across data sharing, intervention design, and implementation (Van Ede et al., 2023). Based on this additional criterion, during the second stage, we re-screened the 55 papers (for both alignment with our definition of PHM and the inclusion of a collaborative approach) which resulted in the final set of seven papers for inclusion in our rapid review. A reference list of the 48 studies excluded at this second screening stage along with reasons for exclusion can be seen in Appendix 1 (Section 9). For further detail on the methods used in this review, please refer to section 6.

2 RESULTS

This section includes an overview of the evidence base. Details of the included study characteristics and PHM approaches used are summarised in Section 2.1 and Table 1. A detailed summary of the key findings, in terms of the effectiveness of each of the different PHM approaches or interventions evaluated, is reported in Sections 2.2.1 to 2.2.3 and Table 2.

2.1 Overview of the Evidence Base

A total of seven comparative primary studies were included in the review. Details of the PHM used in the included studies are presented in Table 1. Three studies were identified that assessed the effectiveness of the overall PHM approach (Stokes et al., 2021; Sioni et al., 2025; Murphy et al., 2018). This included the use of care management models (Sioni et al., 2025), integrated care models (Stokes et al., 2021) and care co-ordinators in the Johns Hopkins community health partnership (J-CHIP) programme (Murphy et al., 2018). In addition, four studies were identified that assessed the effectiveness of specific interventions designed using a PHM approach (Ajibola et al., 2025; Scher et al., 2022; Porter et al., 2020; Hitsman et al., 2022). This included a Social Determinants of Health (SDoH) screening and referral process (Ajibola et al., 2025), a food supplementation service (Scher et al., 2022), a smoking cessation intervention and an exercise intervention (Exercise is Medicine Greenville model [EIMG® model]) Porter et al., 2020).

Various study designs were used. This included one pilot randomised controlled trial (RCT) (Hitsman et al., 2022), two non-randomised controlled studies (Murphy et al., 2018; Stokes et al., 2021), one pilot non-randomised controlled study (Scher et al., 2022), one cohort study (Sioni et al., 2025), one repeated measures study (Ajibola et al., 2025), and one uncontrolled before and after study (Porter et al., 2022). Included studies were published between 2018 and 2025. The majority of included studies were conducted in the USA (n=6) with only one study conducted in the UK (Stokes et al., 2021). The sample sizes ranged from 190 to 363,000 participants.

The target populations varied across studies including those experiencing food insecurity (Ajibola et al., 2025; Scher et al., 2022); financial constraints and transportation access (Ajibola et al., 2025); low-income smokers (Hitsman et al., 2022); high-need high-cost patients

(Sioni et al., 2025) and high-risk patients with one or more chronic condition (Murphy et al., 2018; Porter et al., 2020; Stokes et al., 2021).

A variety of outcomes were reported including service delivery, healthcare utilisation, healthcare outcomes, costs, health related quality of life and patient perceptions/satisfaction. Service delivery outcomes included social determinants of health screening uptake rates, engagement with smoking cessation quitlines; exercise programmes; community programmes; and food supplementation services. Healthcare utilisation outcomes included emergency department visits, hospitalisations, hospital admissions, readmission, emergency admissions, and primary care utilisation. Health outcomes included health related quality of life, smoking cessation, body weight, blood pressure and heart rate. Cost outcomes included cost per member per year, total cost of secondary care per registered patient and year, cost per user of secondary care, and annual scholarship and revenue costs. Patient experience included any outcomes related to the participants' experience or satisfaction with the intervention they received.

The methodological quality of each included study was assessed using a study design specific JBI critical appraisal checklist (Barker et al., 2024; Barker et al., 2023; Moola et al., 2020). All studies were determined to be of low quality and found to have considerable methodological limitations, often due to poor reporting. The pilot RCT (Hitsman et al., 2022) was limited by poor reporting of the randomisation process, a small sample size, incomplete follow-up or poor reporting of the differences between groups in terms of follow-up and a lack of a power calculation. The non-randomised controlled studies (Murphy et al., 2018; Stokes et al., 2021; Scher et al., 2022) were limited by a lack of multiple measurements both pre and post the intervention, incomplete follow-up or poor reporting of the differences between groups in terms of follow-up and a lack of a power calculation. The cohort study was limited by unclear reporting of loss to follow-up, and a lack of multiple measurements both pre and post the intervention. The repeated measures study (Ajibola et al., 2025) was limited by a lack of a control group, poor reporting of participant characteristics, unclear reporting of follow-up and an inadequate measurement process, as the study was executed in three phases and comparisons were made across the phases. Although multiple measurements were collected throughout the interventions, no baseline measurements were obtained. This may have introduced bias in the assessment, detection, and measurement of key outcomes. The uncontrolled before and after study (Porter et al., 2022) was limited by a lack of a control group, a lack of multiple measurements both pre and post the intervention, incomplete follow-up or poor reporting of the differences between groups in terms of follow-up and a lack of a power calculation. The quality appraisal findings for each study can be seen in Section 7.3.

All the included studies were mapped against the equality, diversity and inclusion framework PROGRESS-PLUS (Place of Residence, Race/ ethnicity, Occupation, Gender, Religion/culture, Education, Socio-economic status, Social capital/networks; PLUS refers to additional context-specific personal characteristics that may contribute to health inequalities and incorporate features of relationships and time-dependent relationships) to identify which studies had considered these factors in their analysis. Details of this approach can be seen in section 6.8. The findings showed that only four of the included studies provided some form of subgroup analysis to further explore the impact of the intervention on the PROGRESS-PLUS components (details are provide in section 7.5)

Table 1. PHM approaches used in the included studies

Citation (Country)	Aim	Study intervention	PHM approaches utilised
Studies assessing the effectiveness of PHM approach (n=3)			
Stokes et al., (2021) (UK)	To examine two novel models of integrated care that were implemented in England and that sought to take a more population health management approach. Specifically, their effectiveness was evaluated in terms of patient experience, health outcomes and costs of care ('triple aim'), with a particular focus on the prevention-centred aspects of the care model.	<p>Intervention: Two novel models of integrated (primary and acute) care in Salford and South Somerset, UK, using 'the entire place-based model of care'. In Salford this involved an integrated contact centre for patient navigation, multidisciplinary case management, local neighbourhood groups and activities, such as sports groups, to encourage healthy social behaviours. In South Somerset this included a complex care hub to provide case management and enhanced primary care (19 GP practices) to provide non-medical health coaching for self-management of chronic conditions.</p> <p>Comparator: Usual care in other English sites commonly targeting high-risk patients using case management approaches (all other GP practices in the rest of England; and NHS Rightcare peers).</p>	<p>Collaboration details: The two study sites (Salford and South Somerset) were part of the wider New Models of Care (Vanguard) programme.</p> <p>Salford: Partnership between Salford City Council, NHS Salford Clinical Commissioning Group, Salford Royal NHS Foundation Trust (leading role), Salford Primary Care Together and Greater Manchester Mental Health NHS Foundation Trust.</p> <p>South Somerset: Leadership by Symphony Programme Board, co-located in Yeovil hospital. The Symphony Programme is a collaboration between Yeovil District Hospital NHS Foundation Trust, south Somerset Healthcare GP Federation, Somerset CCG, Somerset Partnership, the voluntary sector in South Somerset (SSVCA) and Somerset County Council.</p> <p>Data informed planning/designing or delivery of care:</p> <p>To identify patients: In Salford, a data-driven risk stratification approach was used to initially select high-risk patients, prioritising older people. In South Somerset, data-driven risk stratification approach to initially select high-risk patients, prioritising multimorbid people.</p> <p>To determine impact: For measuring patient experience and health status, the national General Practitioner Patient Survey (GPPS) was used. To assess health care costs, the Hospital Episode Statistics (HES) database for England (from April 2009 to March 2018) was used. This database includes administrative data recording all patient contacts with National Health Service (NHS) hospitals.</p> <p>Type of intervention: Proactive, targeted, personalised.</p> <p>Support services: Designed to improve care delivery to populations now and in the future.</p>
Sioni et al., (2025)	To examine whether a proactive, SDoH-focused care management model can (1) reduce ED visits, hospital admissions, and costs; (2) improve patient-reported	<p>Intervention: The care management model involved monthly SDoH reassessments to identify social barriers, real-time admission-discharge-transfer (ADT) alerts triggering outreach, medication management and appointment coordination.</p>	<p>Collaboration details: Care managers consulted with internal providers and external community-based organizations (e.g., social workers or pharmacists) to address culturally tailored or complex needs.</p> <p>Data informed planning/designing or delivery of care: An integrated linked dataset was created to support the tracking of healthcare utilisation and patient reported outcomes.</p>

	outcomes (health-related quality of life, satisfaction); and (3) identify subgroup variations pertinent to equity.	Comparator: Usual care without monthly SDOH checks, involving standard office visits and ad hoc clinician-led interventions.	<p>To identify patients: Administrative claims were used to identify high-need high-cost patients (those with two or more hospital admissions or four or more emergency department visits in the previous 6-months)</p> <p>To support delivery: A health information exchange platform was used to generate real-time ADT alerts</p> <p>To determine impact: EHR records were used to capture demographics, clinical information, SDOH checks and baseline health status and patient satisfaction, administrative claims were used to collect healthcare utilisation and pharmacy records, and pharmacy logs were used to record prescription collections, missed refills or potential non-adherence.</p> <p>Type of intervention: Proactive, targeted, personalised.</p> <p>Support services: Designed to improve care delivery to populations now.</p>
Murphy et al., (2018) (USA)	To report the impact of a community-based programme, the Johns Hopkins Community Health Partnership (J-CHiP) on cost and utilization from 2011 to 2016. The program was designed to improve care coordination and address clinical and social determinants of health.	<p>Intervention: The J-CHiP, a community-based programme for high risk, chronically ill Medicaid and Medicare beneficiaries involved the formation of multidisciplinary care co-ordination teams. Those with chronic medical needs were provided with care coordination by care managers. Those with depression, bipolar, anxiety, obesity, or substance abuse issues were referred to health behaviour specialists who developed treatment plans, delivered disease specific, protocol-based interventions, and provided referrals for psychiatric and pharmacological treatment.</p> <p>Comparator: Usual care, the comparison group received primary care from any other non-intervention site.</p>	<p>Collaboration details: Multidisciplinary care coordination teams were formed within primary care sites, including care managers (CM), health behaviour specialists (HBS), and community health workers, as well as neighbourhood navigators for residents in designated neighbourhoods. Collaboration with community-based organizations (ie, Sisters Together and Reaching and the Men and Families Center).</p> <p>Data informed planning/designing or delivery of care:</p> <p>To identify patients: high risk, chronically ill patients were identified based on their risk of future hospitalisation, as indicated by predictive modelling, or through physician referral.</p> <p>To determine impact: The evaluation uses health plan enrolment data, claims, programme records, Johns Hopkins Adjusted Clinical Groups (ACG) risk data, and predictive risk scores.</p> <p>Type of intervention: Proactive, targeted, personalised</p> <p>Support services: Designed to meet the needs of communities today and in the future.</p>
Studies assessing the effectiveness of specific interventions designed using a PHM approach (n=4)			
Ajibola et al., (2025) (USA)	To examine how leveraging an Electronic Health Record (EHR) system can facilitate Social Determinants of Health (SDoH)	Intervention: A SDoH screening and referral process to identify vulnerable patients experiencing food insecurity, financial hardship, and transportation needs and support the referral to services to address these needs.	<p>Collaboration details: Collaboration between primary care sites, FindHelp.org (a national database of assistance programs for patients with social needs) and community partnerships (details not specified but partnerships made to address the needs identified through the referrals).</p> <p>Data informed planning/designing or delivery of care:</p>

	screening and its integration into Primary Care encounters, while also using the data collected to meet the identified needs.	Comparator: Different years of the intervention.	<p>To identify patients: The intervention included SDoH screening prompts integrated into the EHR to identify patients with unmet social needs.</p> <p>To determine impact: The number of referrals and how many resulted in resource allocation was recorded.</p> <p>Type of intervention: Proactive, targeted, personalised.</p> <p>Support services: Designed to meet the needs of communities today.</p>
Scher et al., (2022) (USA)	To assess the feasibility of a partnership between Henry Ford Health System (HFHS) and Gleaners Community Foodbank of Southeastern Michigan to implement and evaluate a food supplementation intervention initiated in a hospital outpatient clinic setting.	<p>Intervention: The food supplementation intervention (Henry's Groceries for Health program) was designed by the HFHS Population Health Management Department in collaboration with Gleaners and the HFHS Department of Public Health Sciences.</p> <p>Comparator: Historical controls.</p>	<p>Collaboration details: A partnership between a large clinically integrated health system (Henry Ford Health System, HFHS) and a local community food bank (Gleaners Community Foodbank). The food supplementation intervention (Henry's Groceries for Health program) was designed by the HFHS Population Health Management Department in collaboration with Gleaners and the HFHS Department of Public Health Sciences.</p> <p>Data informed planning/designing or delivery of care:</p> <p>To identify patients: The Hunger Vital Signs was used to screen HFHS internal medicine patients to identify those facing food insecurity.</p> <p>To support delivery: Data sharing infrastructure and agreements were established that were necessary for the health system - community organisation (HFHS-Gleaners) partnership that would allow home delivery of food to patients screened for food insecurity in a clinical setting.</p> <p>To determine impact: Electronic health records were used to collect study outcomes and construct a historical comparison group.</p> <p>Type of intervention: Proactive, targeted, personalised.</p> <p>Support services: Designed to meet the needs of communities today.</p>
Porter et al., (2022) (USA)	This paper describes in brief the design and implementation of the Exercise is Medicine Greenville model (EIMG®), through a first-of-its-kind partnership between a medical school, large healthcare system, and community organisation to comprehensively integrate physical activity as a	<p>Intervention: The EIMG® model refers patients with a diagnosis of physical inactivity and/or noncommunicable disease to community partners who provide physical activity interventions. Scholarships are provided to ensure those facing financial constraints were able to engage.</p> <p>Comparator: Before and after</p>	<p>Collaboration details: The University of South Carolina School of Medicine Greenville, Prisma Health, and YMCA of Greenville.</p> <p>Data informed planning/designing or delivery of care:</p> <p>To identify patients: The Physical Activity Vital Sign 2-question prompt, EIMG® best practice alerts, risk assessment, and order sets were integrated into the electronic health record (EHR) to identify those at risk (inactive or had a chronic condition).</p> <p>To support delivery: Patients' financial situation was determined to assess whether the patient needed financial assistance, this information was shared with the YMCA who provided the scholarships.</p> <p>To determine impact: All patient activity (session completion, contraindications to exercise notifications, graduation, or discontinuation), was documented</p>

	<p>primary prevention strategy into their health system.</p>		<p>by the EIMG® Pros and sent through secure fax to the EIMG® Referral Team. The EIMG® Referral Team then provides the patient's summary back to the Healthcare providers (HCP) through the EHR.</p> <p>Type of intervention: Proactive, targeted, personalised</p> <p>Support services: Designed to meet the needs of communities today.</p>
<p>Hitsman et al., (2022) (USA)</p>	<p>This study evaluated the effectiveness of a person-centered and electronic health record (EHR)-automated population health management (PHM) intervention for smoking cessation that was embedded in a community health center primary care setting and designed to engage low-income smokers outside of the primary care visit.</p>	<p>Intervention: A person-centered EHR-automated PHM intervention for smoking cessation, including a letter, text messaging and pro-active e-referral to a quitline, support from a quitline counsellor and a free 8-week course of nicotine replacement therapy.</p> <p>Comparator: Enhanced usual care, where participants are asked about their smoking status, advised to quit using clear and strong language, and e-referred following usual practice.</p>	<p>Collaboration details: Collaboration between primary care community health center (Near North Health Service Corporation) and the Illinois Tobacco Quitline (ITQL), supported by Alliance- Chicago (a Health Resources and Services Administration-funded network that provides a health information technology and collaboration infrastructure). The text messaging component of the intervention was automated by TouchPointCare, a telehealth system service provider.</p> <p>Data informed planning/designing or delivery of care: To identify patients: Structured query language (SQL) was used to analyse EHR data monthly to identify low-income smokers. To support delivery: Data was shared through bidirectional e-referral between the EHR and ITQL. All information received from the ITQL was documented within the patient's EHR.</p> <p>Type of intervention: Proactive, targeted, personalised.</p> <p>Support services: Designed to meet the needs of communities today.</p>

2.2 Summary of the findings

In this section, a narrative summary of the key findings is provided. There was considerable variation between the type of interventions evaluated by included studies, and therefore a narrative summary of the evidence underpinning each intervention is presented separately and no overall synthesis was conducted. Studies assessing the effectiveness of PHM approaches are reported first (n=3) followed by studies assessing the effectiveness of specific interventions designed using a PHM approach (n=4). Each narrative summary includes details of the PHM approach or intervention evaluated as reported by study authors, followed by a summary of the findings. The available evidence for each intervention was assessed based on the design, quality of the evidence, and direction of effect. The PHM approached used is also summarised in table 1 and findings are summarised in Table 2.

2.2.1 The effectiveness of PHM approach

2.2.1.1 Prevention focused integrated care models

Stokes et al (2021) examined the effectiveness of two integrated care models in Salford and South Somerset in England, in relation to patient experience, health outcomes and costs of care (the 'triple aim'). The study was a non-randomised controlled study and was deemed to be of low quality.

In relation to the PHM approach used, although this was poorly defined, study authors reported aspects including data-driven risk stratification to identify patients and cross sector, multidisciplinary collaboration supported integrated care.

The sites received government funding and support to pilot population health management approaches. Salford and South Somerset implemented 'integrated primary and acute care systems' (PACS), seeking to achieve the triple aim. Salford Together was a cross-sector collaborative partnership between Salford City Council, NHS Salford Clinical Commissioning Group, Salford Royal NHS Foundation Trust (leading role), Salford Primary Care Together and Greater Manchester Mental Health NHS Foundation Trust. A data-driven risk stratification process was used to identify high-risk patients initially prioritising older people (although no details about what this involved were reported). System changes implemented at Salford included an integrated contact centre for patients' navigation, multidisciplinary group case management, investment in local neighbourhood groups to encourage community engagement in health social behaviours. There was also some joining of health and social care records (but little information provided on this).

In south Somerset the Symphony Programme was a cross-sector collaboration between Yeovil District Hospital NHS Foundation Trust, south Somerset Healthcare GP Federation, Somerset CCG, Somerset Partnership, the voluntary sector in South Somerset (SSVCA) and Somerset County Council. A data-driven risk stratification process was used to identify high-risk patients initially prioritising people with multimorbidity (although no details about what this involved were reported). System changes implemented in South Somerset included a complex care hub (for case management), enhanced primary care (non-medical health coaching for self-management), an online care plan tool for self-management, telehealth management.

Two usual care control groups were included: all other GP practices in the rest of England; and NHS Rightcare peers (the ten most similar geographical areas). Data used included the General Practitioner Patient Survey (GPPS) for patient experience and health status. The

Hospital Episode Statistics (HES) database for England was used to assess healthcare costs. Outcomes included emergency admissions, primary care utilisation, total cost of secondary care per registered patient per year, cost per user of secondary care, patient reported perceived support for long term conditions and health related quality of life. The key findings are reported below.

Healthcare utilisation

Emergency admissions

Stokes et al., (2021) found that there was a small, but statistically significant increase in ambulatory care sensitive condition (ACSC) emergency admissions in the South Somerset site. The intervention effect was 0.005 (95% CI:0.002 to 0.01; $p<0.001$) when compared to the rest of England controls and 0.004 (95% CI:0.002 to 0.01; $p<0.05$) when compared to Rightcare controls, at an additional 5 admissions per 1000 registered patients per year. No significant differences were reported for the Salford site. When looking at the sub-group analysis of those with multimorbidity, similar findings were reported with no significant differences being reported for the Salford site. However, a significant increase in ACSC emergency admissions was found for the those with multimorbidity at the South Somerset site when compared to the rest of England controls (Intervention effect: 0.008; 95% CI:0.03 to 0.01; $p<0.001$) and when compared to Rightcare controls (Intervention effect: 0.006; 95% CI:0.0004 to 0.01; $p<0.05$).

Primary care utilisation

Stokes et al., (2021) found no effects on primary care utilisation (participants reporting seeing a General Practitioner or nurse within the previous 6 months) in either intervention site. In Salford, the intervention effect was -0.005 (95% CI:-0.02 to 0.01) when compared to the rest of England controls and -0.002 (95% CI:-0.02 to 0.01) when compared to Rightcare controls. In South Somerset the intervention effect was 0.001 (95% CI:-0.01 to 0.01) when compared to the rest of England controls and 0.003 (95% CI:-0.01 to 0.02) when compared to Rightcare controls. Findings identified an initial increase in primary care utilisation in the first six months in South Somerset. Similar trends were observed for Salford, but these were not statistically different from control sites, and neither were sustained over time. Similarly, a sub-group analysis for those with multimorbidity also showed no effects on primary care utilisation for either site. In Salford, the intervention effect was 0.003 (95% CI:-0.01 to 0.19) when compared to the rest of England controls and 0.005 (95% CI:-0.01 to 0.02) when compared to Rightcare controls. In South Somerset the intervention effect was -0.001 (95% CI:-0.01 to 0.01) when compared to the rest of England controls and 0.002 (95% CI:-0.01 to 0.02) when compared to Rightcare controls.

Health outcome

Health related quality of life

Stokes et al., (2021) reported that no significant differences were found between the intervention and control groups in relation to health-related quality of life using the EQ-5D 5 L index. In Salford the intervention effect was 0.005 (95%CI: -0.02 to 0.01) compared to the rest of England controls and 0.003 (95% CI: -0.02 to 0.01) compared to Rightcare controls. In South Somerset the intervention effect was 0.007 (95%CI: -0.02 to 0.01) compared to the rest of England controls and 0.012 (95% CI: -0.03 to 0.004) compared to Rightcare controls.

Costs

Total cost of secondary care per registered patient per year

Stokes et al., (2021) found there was a statistically significant increase in the costs of secondary care over the post-intervention period in both intervention sites, at £73.81 per registered patient per year in Salford and £44.55 in South Somerset. In Salford the intervention effect was 73.87 (95% CI:37.64 to 109.97; $p < 0.001$) when compared to the rest of England controls and 136.57 (95% CI:62.098 to 211.05; $p < 0.001$) when compared to the Rightcare controls. In South Somerset the intervention effect was 44.55 (95% CI:20.35 to 68.74; $p < 0.001$) when compared to the rest of England controls and 83.77 (95% CI:40.97 to 126.58; $p < 0.001$) when compared to the Rightcare controls. When looking at the sub-group analysis for those with multimorbidity, the results showed that South Somerset had consistently higher total costs of secondary care for multi-morbid patients (their primary target group), whereas Salford did not. In Salford the intervention effect was 26.67 (95% CI: -31.596 to 84.94) when compared to the rest of England controls and 101.03 (95% CI: -4.099 to 206.15) when compared to Rightcare controls. Whereas in South Somerset the intervention effect was 80.79 (95% CI:44.84 to 116.74; $p < 0.001$) when compared to the rest of England controls and 103.62 (95% CI:57.54 to 149.696; $p < 0.001$) when compared to Rightcare controls.

Cost per user of secondary care

Stokes et al., (2021) found there was a statistically significant increase in the total cost of secondary care per user at both intervention sites. In Salford, the total cost of secondary care increased by approximately £138 per person per year, the intervention effect was 138.47 (95% CI:76.38 to 200.57; $p < 0.001$) when compared to rest of England controls and 156.61 (95% CI:57.47 to 255.75; $p < 0.05$) when compared to Rightcare controls. In South Somerset, the total cost of secondary care per user increased by approximately £130 per person per year, the intervention effect was 129.72 (95% CI:68.26 to 191.18; $p < 0.001$) when compared to rest of England controls and 168.39 (95% CI:93.88 to 242.89; $p < 0.001$) when compared to Rightcare controls. When looking at the sub-group analysis for those with multimorbidity the increases in cost per user were higher compared to the whole population. In Salford the total cost of secondary care per user increased by approximately £173 per person per year, the intervention effect was 173.36 (95% CI:53.65 to 293.06; $p < 0.05$) when compared to rest of England controls and 209.22 (95% CI:22.29 to 396.14; $p < 0.05$) when compared to Rightcare controls. In South Somerset the total cost of secondary care per user increased by approximately £268 per person per year, the intervention effect was 267.69 (95% CI:150.84 to 384.54; $p < 0.001$) when compared to rest of England controls and 328.63 (95% CI:184.76 to 472.495; $p < 0.001$) when compared to Rightcare controls.

Patient perspective

Perceived support for long term conditions

Stokes et al., (2021) found there were no statistically significant differences in intervention sites compared to controls in terms of patient experience. In Salford the intervention effect was 0.017 (95% CI:-0.02 to 0.05) compared to the rest of England controls and 0.001 (95% CI:-0.04 to 0.04) compared to Rightcare controls. In South Somerset the intervention

effect was 0.02 (95% CI:-0.02 to 0.06) compared to the rest of England controls and 0.008 (95% CI:-0.04 to 0.06) compared to Rightcare controls. However, the study authors state that the intervention effect varied over time and by site. A statistically significant increase in patient experience of care in South Somerset at the end of year one was reported however, no data was provided for this.

2.2.1.2 Social determinants of health focused care model

Sioni et al., (2025) examined whether a proactive, SDoH-focused care management model for high-need high-cost patients could reduce ED visits, hospital admissions, and costs, improve patient-reported outcomes, and identify sub-group variations. The study was a cohort study and was deemed to be low quality.

In relation to the PHM approach used, although this was poorly defined, study authors reported aspects including administrative claims data to identify those considered to be high need high cost, and multidisciplinary and cross-sector collaboration to facilitate care management.

The care management model consisted of four parts: monthly SDoH screening; real time admission-discharge transfer (ADT) alerts; medication management and appointment coordination. Care managers conducted monthly SDoH reassessments, performed medication checks, and responded to the ADT notifications. Care managers also consulted with internal providers and external community-based organizations (e.g., social workers or pharmacists) to address culturally tailored or complex needs.

Patients were determined to be high need high cost if they'd had 2 or more hospital admissions or 4 or more ED visits in the previous 6 months. An integrated dataset was created to support tracking of healthcare utilisation changes. This included data from the EHR, administrative claims, health information exchange platform and pharmacy logs. EHR data included demographics, clinical details, SDoH checks, health-related quality of life and patient satisfaction. Administrative claims data included ED visits, hospital admissions and pharmacy records. Health information exchange platform data included the real-time ADT alerts, enabling post-discharge outreach. Pharmacy logs were used to verify prescription collections and flag missed refills or non-adherence. The comparison group received usual care.

Outcomes included ED visits, hospital admissions, the mean cost per person, health-related quality of life and patient satisfaction. The key findings are reported below.

Healthcare utilisation

Emergency Department (ED) visits

Sioni et al., (2025) reported that the number of ED visits per person was found to reduce for the intervention group compared to the comparison group at day 7, day 30 and day 60. A day 7 this reduction was not statistically significant when compared to controls (-0.03; 95% CI: -0.06 to 0; p=0.08), however the differences at day 30 (-0.13 95%CI: -0.18 to -0.08; p<0.001) and day 60 were statistically significant (-0.17; 95%CI: -0.23 to -0.11; p<0.001).

Hospital admissions

Sioni et al., (2025) reported that the number of hospital admissions per person was found to reduce for the intervention group compared to the comparison group at all time points. The between group differences were statistically significant at day 7 (-0.08; 95% CI:-0.11 to -0.05; $p<0.001$), day 30 (-0.08; 95% CI:-0.12 to -0.04; $p<0.001$) and day 60 (-0.12 95% CI:-0.17 to -0.07; $p<0.001$).

Health outcome

Health-related quality of life

Sioni et al., (2025) assessed health-related quality of life using EQ-5D-5L scores. The intervention group scores significantly improved from 0.720 to 0.802 ($t[525] = -14.88$, $p<0.001$), whereas the comparison group's increase (0.604 to 0.612) was not significant ($t[262] = -1.88$, $p=0.069$). A sub-group analysis also showed that middle-aged adults aged 36-50 with private medical insurance had the largest increase in health-related quality of life (+0.137; 95% CI:0.115 to 0.159). The authors also state that some non-White cohorts exhibited smaller EQ-5D-5L gains, however details of the scores were not reported.

Costs

Mean cost per person

Sioni et al., (2025) reported that the mean cost per person was reduced from \$6,019 pre-enrolment to \$2,422 post-enrolment, showing a statistically significant decrease of \$3,222 ($p<0.001$). The return on investment was calculated as net savings divided by total intervention costs, the return on investment ratio was estimated to be 6.87:1 return on investment. This suggests that for every one dollar invested in the staff salaries \$6.87 were saved in avoided acute-care costs within two months.

Patient perspectives

Patient satisfaction

Sioni et al., (2025) assessed patient satisfaction using the Net Promoter Score (NPS). The intervention groups' increase was statistically significant (from 19.49 to 28.22; $t[525]=-43.12$; $p<0.001$) whereas the change in the comparison group was not (from 16.26 to 15.55; $t[262]=1.71$; $p<0.09$). A sub-group analysis showed the biggest gain in patient satisfaction (+9.56 points) was reported for younger adults aged 18 to 35 with private insurance.

2.2.1.3 Community-based intervention designed to improve care coordination and address clinical and social determinants of health

Murphy et al (2018) reported the impact of the Johns Hopkins Community Health Partnership (J-CHIP) community-based programme for high risk, chronically ill patients receiving Medicaid and Medicare. The programme was designed to improve care coordination and address the clinical and social determinants of health. The study was a non-randomised controlled study which was deemed to be of low quality.

In relation to the PHM approach used, although this was poorly defined, study authors reported aspects including predictive modelling or physician referral to identify high risk, chronically ill patients, and cross sector collaboration to connect patients with community services.

Multidisciplinary care coordination teams were formed within primary care sites which included primary care providers, care managers (CM), health behaviour specialists (HBS), and community health workers, as well as neighbourhood navigators. Health plan enrolment data, claims, program records, Johns Hopkins Adjusted Clinical Groups (ACG) risk data, and predictive risk scores were utilised throughout the study. Participants were chronically ill adults who were identified through predictive modelling or physician referral as being high risk of future hospitalisation. Community health workers reached out to potential participants and assessed their clinical and social needs. Those with complex medical needs were referred to CMs to provide care co-ordination. Those with behavioural health needs were referred to HBSs who assessed their needs, developed treatment plans and provided disease-specific interventions and referrals for psychiatric and pharmacological treatment. Patients may have also received social support and connection to community services through the neighbourhood manager. Cross-sector collaboration with community-based organizations (Sisters Together and Reaching and the Men and Families Centre) supported the community health worker and neighbourhood navigator in addressing the social determinants of health. A comparison group included patients who received primary care from any other non-intervention site.

Outcomes included ED visits, hospital admissions, readmissions and costs per member per year. The key findings are reported below.

Healthcare utilisation

Emergency department (ED) visits

Murphy et al., (2018) found that the impact on the number of ED visits was mixed. The ratio of incident rate ratios (IRRs) of ED visits for the intervention group showed a small improvement compared the comparison group for Medicaid (IRR:0.97; 95% CI:0.81 to 1.14) but this was slightly worse when compared to those in the Medicare group (IRR:1.02; 95% CI:0.86 to 1.20), although neither were statistically significant. For the care managers cohort, both payers exhibited similar results for participants and nonparticipants in relation to ED visits (IRR=0.99; Medicaid 95% CI:0.8 to 1.18; Medicare 95% CI:0.82 to 1.19). For the health behaviour specialist cohort, the IRRs increased more for participants than nonparticipants (IRR=1.08; 95% CI:0.82 to 1.37) for Medicaid and (IRR:1.09; 95% CI:0.8 to 1.48) for Medicare, although the increases were not statistically significant.

Hospital admissions

Murphy et al., (2018) found that hospital admission and readmission rates combined were 9% to 26% lower for those with a Care Manager (CM) and/or Health Behaviour Specialist (HBS) compared to the control group, which was not statistically significant. The authors found non-significant decreases in the admission rate for J-CHiP Medicaid participants in the care managers and health behaviour specialists' cohorts. The ratio of IRRs was 0.91 (95% CI:0.75 to 1.12) for CM and 0.92 (95% CI:0.71 to 1.17) for HBS. The rate for the full Medicaid cohort was relatively unchanged (ratio=1.01; 95% CI:0.83 to 1.22). For Medicare, all 3 cohorts showed an increase in the admission rate for J-CHiP participants as compared with nonparticipants (ratio=1.08; 95% CI:0.90 to 1.27) for full and 1.09 (95% CI:0.91 to 1.32) for CM, and

the increase for the HBS cohort was statistically significant (ratio=1.28, 95% CI:1.01 to 1.65; p<0.05).

Readmissions

Murphy et al., (2018) found that readmission rates varied by insurance status. For Medicaid, the CM and HBS cohorts showed nonsignificant improvements in the number of readmissions. The ratio of IRRs was 0.84; (95% CI:0.52 to 1.42) for CM and 0.74 (95% CI:0.46 to 1.33) for HBS, although the full cohort did not experience the same improvement (ratio of IRRs= 1.03; 95% CI:0.65 to 1.67). However, for Medicare, all 3 cohorts exhibited increases in the readmission rate that were larger than the changes for the comparison group. The ratio of IRRs was 1.29; (95% CI:0.73 to 2.28) for the full cohort, 1.29 (95% CI:0.70 to 2.37) for CM, and 1.24 (95% CI:0.66 to 2.33) for HBS, although none were found to be statistically significant.

Costs

Cost per member per year (PMPY)

Murphy et al., (2018) found that costs increased for both the intervention and comparator groups when comparing costs before and after the intervention, but that the increases were generally smaller for the intervention group. For the full Medicaid group, a cost increase of \$2,536 PMPY was identified compared to a cost increase of \$3,706 PMPY for the comparator group. This represents a cost saving of \$1,171 PMPY, although the difference was not statistically significant (95% CI:-\$4,968 to \$2,145). A similar non statistically significant trend was reported for the Medicare group, however the difference between the intervention and control groups was smaller (-\$476 PMPY; 95% CI:-\$4,148 to \$3,024). The results for the CM and HBS cohorts were also found to vary by payer. For the CM group, cost savings for participants were reported for Medicaid (-\$3,051 PMPY; 95% CI:-\$7,517 to \$994) and Medicare (-\$246 PMPY; 95% CI:-\$4,033 to \$3,307), neither of which were statistically significant. For the HBS cohort, non-significant cost savings were reported for Medicaid (-\$2,038 PMPY; 95% CI:-\$7,236 to \$3,157), however intervention participants receiving Medicare showed a cost increase when compared to the comparator group (\$1,980 PMPY; 95% CI:-\$4,231 to \$8,371) although this was also not statistically significant. After accounting for implementation costs, these results reflect a return on investment ranging from -2% for the full cohort to 154% for the subset that received more intensive services with a Care Manager (whether this was statistically significant was not reported). For Medicaid participants, costs were almost \$1200 per member per year lower for participants as a whole, \$2000 lower for those with a Health Behaviour Specialist, and \$3000 lower for those with a Care Manager. For Medicare participants, costs were lower (-\$476). However, none of the observed Medicaid or Medicare differences were statistically significant.

2.2.2 Bottom line summary of studies assessing the effectiveness of the overall PHM approach

The findings for studies assessing the effectiveness of overall PHM approaches appear to be mixed.

In terms of healthcare utilisation, the SDoH focused care model led to a reduced number of ED visits and reduced hospital admissions. However, the integrated care models and the J-

CHIP programme found some variation in findings based on the individual sites being studied or by health insurance payer type. The integrated care models showed no differences in terms of primary care utilisation when compared to controls but did find increased emergency admissions (which significantly increased for those at the South Somerset site, but no significant differences were reported for those at Salford, this was consistent when looking at those with multimorbidity). The J-CHIP programme also found mixed results for the number of ED visits (reduced for Medicaid, increased for Medicare but neither statistically significant), hospital admissions (only significantly increasing for the HBS cohort receiving Medicare) and readmissions (reduced for CM and HBS cohorts receiving Medicaid, but increased for all cohorts receiving Medicare, however neither were statistically significant). Therefore, in terms of healthcare utilisation visits to ED, primary care utilisation and hospital admissions varied across the studies.

In terms of health outcome, two studies reported health-related quality of life. The care management model found patients' health related quality of life was seen to improve, with the biggest improvements were reported by middle aged adults with private medical insurance, and smaller improvements were reported by some non-White cohorts. However, the integrated care models showed no impact on health-related quality of life.

In terms of costs, the integrated care models found the total cost of secondary care per patient and year were significantly higher for the intervention groups (however costs for those with multimorbidity were only significantly higher at the South Somerset sites). The costs per user of secondary care were also found to significantly increase when compared to controls with even higher costs for those with multimorbidity compared to the whole population. However, the findings from the SDoH focused care model and the J-CHIP programme showed reduced costs per patients suggesting some potential cost savings. However, in the J-CHIP programme neither the cost savings nor cost increases reported were statistically significant and there was some variation in findings depending on payer type. Therefore, in terms of costs, the integrated care model found the total cost of secondary care per patient and year were significantly higher for the intervention groups, but the SDoH focused care model and the J-CHIP programme showed a reduction in cost per patient suggesting some potential savings are possible.

Two studies reported patient perspectives. The care management model found patient satisfaction was improved with the biggest improvement reported for younger adults with private insurance. However, the integrated care models showed no impact on patient perceptions of support for their long-term conditions.

Overall, the evidence for studies assessing the effectiveness of the PHM approaches revealed a mixed picture, likely due to the heterogeneity of the study aims and target populations. In addition, all findings were reported by low-quality studies. As such, our confidence in the findings overall is low and further evidence would be needed to draw any firm conclusions.

2.2.3 Studies assessing the effectiveness of specific interventions designed using PHM approaches

2.2.3.1 Social determinants of health screening and referral process intervention

Ajibola et al., (2025) aimed to develop a screening tool to identify SDoH and to develop a referral workflow for patients with unmet social needs. The study was conducted in three phases

to streamline and improve the screening and referral processes. The study had a repeated measures design and was deemed to be of low quality.

In relation to the PHM approach used, although this was poorly defined, study authors reported aspects including integrate screening data into EHRs to ensure patients' needs were identified and cross-sector collaboration to ensure that support could be offered in a streamlined way.

The development of the screening tool consisted of three phases, each phase involved further refinement based on findings of the previous phase. The screening tool included a set of questions relating to food insecurity, financial constraints, and transportation access. Patients who had a positive screening result (i.e. the patient was identified as in need of assistance in these areas), were then referred to a social worker who tailored assistance to their specific needs and participants were also given access to FindHelp.org website (a national database of assistance programmes) where they could access resources available to them in their area that addressed their identified needs and community partnerships were also established.

Outcomes included the number of patients screened, the number of positive screenings, number of FindHelp.org users and the number of patients connected with programmes through Findhelp.org. The key findings are reported below.

Service delivery

Social determinants of health screening rates

Ajibola et al., (2025) compared the results between the three years of the intervention. The results showed that the number of people who received SDoH screening increased by 95% from 2020 to 2022 with an increase in social work referrals and the allocation of resources to the targeted patient population. In 2020, out of 35,105 patients seen at the centre, 39% (13,704) were screened for SDoH. Out of the 13,704 patients screened, 24% had positive screening results. In 2021, out of the 41,874 patients seen at the centre, 51% (21,167) were screened for SDoH, with 18% of these receiving a positive result. In 2022, out of the 42,335 patients seen, 76% (32,268) were screened for SDoH with 15% receiving a positive screening result. Thus, SDoH screening rates increased from 39% in 2020 to 76% in 2022, which is a 95% increase over the three-year intervention period. However, it is unclear if this increase was statistically significant as this was not reported.

Engagement with community programmes

Ajibola et al., (2025) reported that engagement with FindHelp.org and the number of people successfully being connected to a programme increased over time. In 2020, there were 111 FindHelp.org users, 16 of which were connected to programmes. This rose to 2,283 in 2021 (178 participants connected to programmes) and to 3,888 in 2022 (977 participants connected to programmes). However, it was not reported if the increases were statistically significant. It is also unclear why only some FindHelp.org users were connected to programmes, and not all. In addition, there was no reporting on the number of participants receiving specific programmes or any impact measures as a result of this connection.

2.2.3.2 Food supplementation intervention

Scher et al (2022) aimed to assess the feasibility of a partnership between Henry Ford Health System (HFHS) and Gleaners Community Foodbank of Southeastern Michigan to implement

and evaluate a food supplementation intervention initiated in a hospital outpatient clinic setting. An additional aim was to demonstrate improvement in patient health. The study was a pilot non-randomised controlled trial and was deemed to be of low quality.

In relation to the PHM approach used, although this was poorly defined, study authors reported aspects including screening patients to identify those facing food insecurity and cross-sector collaboration to ensure that support could be offered in a streamlined way.

To achieve the aim a clinic-based screening and referral protocol was implemented as well as developing the infrastructure and data agreements necessary between the two organisations. Patients were screened for food insecurity, using the Hunger Vital Signs which contains two questions to establish if within the last year patients had been worried about whether food would run out, or if the food they bought did not last until they had money to buy more. A positive response to one of the questions triggered an internal referral to a case manager who enrolled the patient into the study. Patients were provided with personalised food supplementation two times a month for a year. Data was collected and managed using an electronic tool, REDCap. This tool was used by both HFHS and Gleaners employees to communicate delivery schedules and record baseline and patient experience surveys. A historical comparison group was also established.

Outcomes included the number of patients screened, the number of food deliveries provided, ED visits and hospitalisations as well as patient satisfaction. The key findings are reported below.

Service delivery

Food deliveries

Scher et al., (2022) reported that 340 out of 353 patients who were found to be food insecure agreed to participate in the study, 97% then agreed to accept food deliveries. This resulted in 6,519 deliveries scheduled of which 5,860 (89.9%) were successfully delivered to the participant.

Healthcare utilisation

Emergency department (ED) visits

Scher et al., (2022) found that 123 patients in the intervention group made 279 ED visits during the 12-month follow-up, representing a -41.5% relative reduction from baseline and a per person average reduction of 0.77 (95% CI:0.40 to 1.15). The historical comparison group also showed significant relative reductions compared to baseline in ED visits (-25.3%) and a per person reduction of 0.34. While smaller in magnitude compared to the intervention group, the reduction was also statistically significant (95% CI:0.09 to 0.59). Difference-in-differences regression analysis was used to determine if the trend in ED visits over time was the same for the intervention group compared to that of the historical comparison group. The trend in ED visits for 12 months for the intervention group was 0.44 (95% CI: -0.01 to 0.88) visits per patient lower than that of the historical comparison group. However, it was not reported if this was statistically significant.

Hospitalisations

Scher et al., (2022) found a greater relative reduction in hospitalisation among the intervention group of -55.9% (unit) compared to a -17.6% relative reduction in the control group and a significant per person reduction in hospitalisation of 0.15 (95% CI:0.01 to 0.29), compared to -0.004 (95% CI:-0.06 to 0.07) per person hospitalisation reduction for the historical comparison group. The difference-in-differences regression analysis showed the trend over time for hospitalisations reduced in the intervention group by 0.15 (95% CI: -0.001 to 0.31) visits per patient lower compared to that of the historical comparison group. However, it was not reported if this was statistically significant.

Patient perspectives

Satisfaction

Scher et al., (2022) reported that 260 patients completed 1.987 surveys over the course of the intervention and follow-up period. Overall, 95.8% of participants reported the food delivered met their needs, 90.7% reported eating all the food, 50.3% reported using the dietary tips and recipes provided and 36.5% reported sharing the meals with other people.

2.2.3.3 Clinic-to-community, physical activity referral intervention

Porter et al., (2022) describes a partnership between the University of South Carolina School of Medicine Greenville, Prisma Health, and the YMCA of Greenville to integrate physical activity as a primary prevention strategy into their health system. The Exercise is Medicine Greenville® model (EIMG®) aimed to achieve a healthier more physically active patient population. The study was uncontrolled comparing findings before and after the programme was initiated and was deemed to be of low quality.

In relation to the PHM approach used, although this was poorly defined, study authors reported aspects including integrating a 2-question prompt into the EHR to identify individual at risk (inactive or had a chronic condition), and cross-sector collaboration to streamline support.

The EIMG® model was implemented in the Prisma Health clinics by integrating the EIMG® best practice alerts, risk assessment, order sets and the Physical Activity Vital Sign 2-question prompt into the EHR. A nurse at the clinic assessed patients' physical activity levels using the 2-question prompt to determine how many minutes per day were spent exercising and how many days/weeks. If a patient was deemed to be physically inactive (<150 min/week of moderate intensity aerobic activity) and/or had a chronic condition (overweight/obesity, hypertension, type 2 diabetes, stable heart disease) they were eligible for the programme. Eligible patients were provided with basic physical activity and health education for exercising with chronic disease, developed by the American College of Sports Medicine experts. They were then electronically referred to the EIMG® Referral Team who reviewed referred their health records and established a preferred location for the patient to attend the physical activity programme. If needed, the EIMG® Referral Coordinator connected the patient with a YMCA financial assistant who provided a scholarship in order to increase accessibility to those who may otherwise have been unable to engage. The EIMG® Pros sent patient activity (session completion, contraindications to exercise notifications, graduation, or discontinuation from the

program) back to the EIMG® Referral Team, who provide the patient's summary to the HCP through the EHR.

The EIMG® exercise training program was created using evidence-based research and was delivered in small groups (≤ 7 patients/ group), over 12 weeks (60-minute sessions, 2 sessions/week). Each training session included an aerobic training component and a full-body resistance training component with the goal for patients to progress to >50 min/session of moderate-to-vigorous intensity exercise by completion of the programme. However, the exercise sessions were delivered to patients based on their individual strengths, their class population, and the specific facility setting. Participants also received EIMG® patient education handouts that provide information on adopting a healthy lifestyle.

Outcomes included the number of people who engaged with, and completed the exercise programme, body weight, blood pressure, heart rate, costs and patient satisfaction. A sub-group analysis was also provided for those with hypertension. The key findings are reported below.

Service delivery

Exercise programme engagement

Porter et al., (2022) reported that enrolment and completion of the exercise programme continued to grow over the study period. Since 2016, 36% (347/973) of participants referred to the programme chose to enrol in the intervention. Overall, between 2016 and 2019 a total of 210 participants (61% of those enrolled) completed the programme by attending at least 80% of the sessions. However, completion rates varied over the study years: 48% (n=15) in 2016; 63% (n=24) in 2017; 68% (n=94) in 2018; and 62% (n=77) in 2019 (on track for completion rate of 72% but the programme was paused for 15 patients during the COVID-19 pandemic).

Health outcomes

Body weight

Porter et al., (2022) found that the EIMG® programme was associated with a statistically significant decrease in mean body weight over the course of the study (data from 2016 to 2019: pre 102.5kg vs post 100.9kg; $p < 0.001$; data from 2018 to 2019: pre 100.2kg vs post 98.2kg; $p < 0.001$). A sub-group analysis reported similarly positive findings for patients with hypertension showing the intervention resulted in a statistically significant decrease in mean body weight after receiving the intervention (data from 2016 to 2019: pre 105.4kg vs post 104kg; $p = 0.001$; data from 2018 to 2019: pre 103.1kg vs post 101.3kg; $p < 0.001$).

Blood pressure and Heart Rate

Porter et al., (2022) reported that engaging in the EIMG® programme resulted in very small reductions in resting heart rate (pre 76bpm vs post 76bpm; $p = 0.916$) and diastolic blood pressure (pre 81mmHg vs post 80mmHg; $p = 0.137$) which were not statistically significant. However, a statistically significant reduction in systolic blood pressure was found after the intervention (pre 128mmHg vs post 126mmHg; $p < 0.05$) when compared with before (data from 2016 to 2019). The data from 2018 to 2019 showed very small reductions in heart rate (pre 76bpm vs post 75 bpm) systolic (pre 128mmHg vs post 126mmHg) and diastolic blood pressure (pre 81mmHg vs post 80 mmHg) after the intervention, none of which were statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). A sub-group analysis for patients with hypertension found no change in resting heart rate (77bpm pre and post) but did show a decrease in systolic (pre 136mmHg vs post 129mmHg) and diastolic (pre 86mmHg vs post 83mmHg) blood pressure, both of which

were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$; data from 2016 to 2019). When looking at the data from 2018 to 2019 heart rate did not significantly change after the intervention (pre 77bpm vs post 76bpm) among people with hypertension, but statistically significant reductions in systolic (pre 136mmHg vs post 129mmHg; $p < 0.001$) and diastolic (pre 86mmHg vs post 82mmHg; $p < 0.001$) blood pressure was found.

Costs

Scholarship provided and revenue generated

Porter et al., (2022) found that the total amount of scholarship (cost to participate in the EIMG® 12-week exercise) provided to those who could not afford to engage with the EIMG® model increased every year (Aug to Dec 2016= \$1,537; Jan to Dec 2017= \$3,686; Jan to Dec 2018= \$7,983; Jan to Dec 2019= \$10,240). However, the total amount of revenue generated by those who could afford the cost to participate also increased every year (Aug to Dec 2016= \$796; Jan to Dec 2017= \$1,791; Jan to Dec 2018= \$5,771; Jan to Dec 2019= \$21,648) exceeding the amount of scholarship provided.

Patient perceptions

Satisfaction

A total of 170 participants completed an exit survey, and it was found that patients reported high satisfaction scores (out of 5) for all aspects of the programme and personnel (Porter et al., 2022). All healthcare providers scores were above 4.75. EIMG® Programme Coordinator and EIMG® Pro satisfaction scores were above 4.9. Perceptions around if the programme helped to improve skills and abilities were above 4.24. Participants reported that: they would recommend the programme to others (4.94); the programme had a positive impact on their physical activity and exercise habits (4.88); they made lasting friends (3.96); they felt better than they did at the start of the programme (4.84), and that exercise will become a part of their lifestyle (4.67).

2.2.3.4 Person-centred smoking cessation intervention

Hitsman et al., (2022) assessed the preliminary effectiveness of an electronic health record (EHR)-automated PHM intervention (Choose to Change) which involved collaboration between the Near North Health Service Corporation (NNHSC) and the Illinois Tobacco Quitline (ITQL), for smoking cessation among diverse low-income adults. The study was a pilot randomised controlled trial which was deemed to be of low quality.

In line with our definition of PHM, this study aimed to improve population health. Financial barriers were removed by providing nicotine replacement therapy for free. Patients received targeted and personalised care to support smoking cessation to address the needs of the community today.

In relation to the PHM approach used, although this was poorly defined, study authors reported aspects including structured query language (SQL) to analyse EHR data monthly to identify

eligible patients, and cross-sector collaboration to ensure that smokers could be connected with a quitline and treatments in a streamlined way.

Patients of NNHSC were identified based on information in the EHR to identify those who were considered as a “current someday smoker” or a “current every day smoker” and had one or more provider visits within the past year. The intervention involved e-referral to the quitline; a single-page letter that encouraged cessation or reduction (developed through patient focus groups and guided by self-determination theory); and five text messages that reinforced message in the letter. Supported by Alliance-Chicago (a Health Resources and Services Administration-funded network), the EHR system was used by the NNHSC for all clinical encounters. Physicians referred patients to the ITQL through an automated e-referral order, which triggered a referral request through the interface engine Qvera. The order was confirmed through a review of a valid email address showing the bidirectional referral system between the EHR and the ITQL. Once confirmed, the referral request was sent through an automated file to the ITQL, who contacted the patient. Participants were offered smoking cessation or a smoking reduction treatment in English or Spanish. Treatments included a self-help packet and an 8-week course of nicotine replacement therapy for free, which was mailed to participants willing to set a quit date in 2-week allotments. After each session a file was automatically created which included the services provided and the information documented during the call. This was then sent to Alliance-Chicago where fields in the EHR were automatically populated. A summary document from the EHR was then sent to the patient’s primary care provider to relay the referral outcome. All information from the ITQL was documented in the patient’s EHR. Participants in the control group received enhanced usual care.

Outcomes included quitline engagement, smoking cessation treatment engagement, and smoking abstinence. The key findings are reported below.

Service delivery

Quitline engagement

Hitsman et al., (2020) reported the effects of the intervention on quitline engagement and treatment utilisation. Statistically significant differences were reported in those who engaged in quitline treatment at week 6 and week 14. At week 6, 25/97 participants in the intervention group engaged with the quitline, compared to 0/92 participants from the control group; (OR=0.00; 95% CI:0.00 to 0.13; $p<0.0001$). At week 14, 21/97 participants in the intervention group engaged compared to 0/92 control group participants (OR=0.00; 95% CI:0.00 to 0.17; $p<0.0001$).

Smoking cessation treatment engagement

Hitsman et al., (2020) reported that of the 25 intervention group participants who engaged with the quitline, all received cessation-focused behavioural counselling and 92% (23/25) received NRT, whereas in the control group 4 participants reported receiving smoking cessation counselling and 20 participants reported using NRT.

Healthcare outcomes

Smoking abstinence

Hitsman et al., (2020) reported abstinence rates at three time points. At week 6, more people in the control group reported abstinence when compared to the intervention group, however,

this difference was not statistically significant (4/93 vs 2/97 respectively; OR=2.13; 95% CI:0.30 to 24.05; p=0.437). At week 14 (9/97 vs 3/93 respectively; OR=0.33; 95% CI:0.06 to 1.37; p=0.134) and week 28 (8/49 vs 3/47 respectively; OR=0.35; 95% CI:0.06 to 1.60; p=0.199) more people in the intervention group reported abstinence than in the control group, however, these differences were not statistically significant.

2.2.4 Bottom line summary of studies assessing the effectiveness of specific interventions designed using PHM approaches

The findings for studies assessing the effectiveness of specific interventions designed using a PHM approach appear to be in favour of the interventions.

There is evidence to suggest that specific interventions designed using a PHM approach can improve service delivery in terms of increased screening and referral amongst those who need it most, as well as increased engagement in exercise and smoking cessation services.

Healthcare utilisation was reported by a single study, the food supplementation programme. This found a reduction in ED visits and admissions.

Healthcare outcomes were also positive. The EIMG referral model led to decreased body weight and systolic blood pressure for the whole sample, and smoking abstinence was increased in the intervention group at weeks 14 and 28.

In terms of costs, the EIMG referral model generated more revenue from those who could afford to pay to participate than the amount of scholarship provided to those who otherwise could not afford to pay to participate.

In terms of patient perspectives, two studies reported this outcome. Patients reported that the food supplementation programme met their needs and patients who attended the EIMG referral model exercise programme reported high levels of satisfaction with the programme and those delivering the programme.

Overall, the evidence suggests specific interventions designed using a PHM approach can lead to increased service delivery, reduced healthcare utilisation, improved health outcomes, and were generally well accepted by participants. However, as the specific interventions had varying aims for varying population groups and were all reported by low-quality studies our confidence in the findings overall is low and further evidence would be needed to draw any firm conclusions.

Table 2. Summary of findings

Studies Country	Study design	Population	Intervention	Comparator	Impact of intervention S Statistically significant ^U Significance not reported ^{NS} Not statistically significant	Acceptability of intervention	Quality of the evidence
Studies assessing the effectiveness of a PHM approach (n=3)							
Stokes et al., (2021) UK	Non-randomised controlled study	Older adults or those with multimorbidity	Integrated care models (implemented across two NHS vanguard sites)	Usual care	In comparison to control group, the intervention led to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased emergency admissions in South Somerset^S - Increased total cost of secondary care per patient and year^S - Increased cost per user of secondary care^S - Increased cost per user of secondary care for those with multimorbidity^S No impact found on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary care utilisations when compared to controls at either site. - Emergency admissions at Salford site compared to controls. - Health-related quality of life. 	Experience: Integrated care models had no impact on patient perceptions of support for their long-term conditions.	Study rated as low quality due to poor conduct and reporting.
Sioni et al., (2025) USA	Cohort study	High-need, high-cost patients	A social determinants of health focused care management model	Usual care	Appeared to be effective at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reducing ED visits compared to controls at day 7^{NS}, day 30^S, and day 60^S - Reducing hospital admissions compared to controls at all time points^S - Reducing mean cost per patient^S - Improving health related quality of life^S 	Satisfaction Care management model improved patient satisfaction ^S	Study rated as low quality due to poor conduct and reporting.
Murphy et al., (2018) USA	Non-randomised controlled study	Patients with one or more chronic conditions	Community-based programme designed to improve care coordination and address clinical and social determinants of	Usual care	Appeared to be effective at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reducing costs per member per year when compared to controls^{NS} Impact was mixed* for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ED visits^{NS} - Hospital admissions^{NS} - Readmissions^{NS} In the HBS cohort, the intervention led to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased ED Visits^{NS} 	Not reported	Study rated as low quality due to poor conduct and reporting.

Studies Country	Study design	Population	Intervention	Comparator	Impact of intervention S Statistically significant ^U Significance not reported ^{NS} Not statistically significant	Acceptability of intervention	Quality of the evidence
			health (J-CHIP)		* Findings varied by insurance type and level, with some having positive impacts and others negative.		
Studies assessing the effectiveness of specific interventions designed using a PHM approach (n=4)							
Ajibola et al., (2025) USA	Repeated measures study	Those experiencing food insecurity, financial constraints, and transportation access issues Patients attending primary care (intervention used to identify those experiencing food insecurity, financial constraints, or transportation access issues)	Social determinants of health screening and referral to FindHelp.org (providing links to community services)	Pervious years of the intervention	Appeared to be effective at: - Increasing social determinants of health screening ^U - Increasing engagement with community resources ^U	Not reported	Study rated as low quality due to poor conduct and reporting.
Scher et al., (2022) USA	Pilot non-randomised controlled study	Those experiencing food insecurity	Food supplementation	Historical controls	Appeared to be effective at: - Increasing engagement with food supplementation service ^U - Reducing emergency department visits ^U - Reducing hospitalisation ^U	Satisfaction: Food supplementation was well received by participants who reported being satisfied the food met their needs.	Study rated as low quality due to poor conduct and reporting.
Porter et al., (2022) USA	Uncontrolled before and after study	Those who were inactive and/or had a chronic condition	A clinic-to-community physical activity referral intervention	Before and after the intervention	Appeared to be effective at: - Increasing exercise engagement ^U - Reducing body weight ^S - Reducing body weight for those with hypertension ^S - Reducing systolic blood pressure ^S	Satisfaction: EIMG exercise programme appeared well received by all participants reporting high levels of satisfaction with the	Study rated as low quality due to poor conduct and reporting.

Studies Country	Study design	Population	Intervention	Comparator	Impact of intervention S Statistically significant U Significance not reported NS Not statistically significant	Acceptability of intervention	Quality of the evidence
			(EIMG® model)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reducing systolic and diastolic blood pressure in those with hypertension^S - Generating revenue^U No effects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No significant difference was found on diastolic blood pressure for whole sample after the intervention 	programme and programme personnel.	
Hitsman et al., (2022) USA	Pilot RCT	Low-income smokers	Person-centred smoking cessation intervention	Enhanced usual care, participants were e-referred following usual practice.	Appeared to be effective at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing quitline engagement at weeks 6 and 14^S - Increased engagement with smoking cessation treatments^U - Increasing smoking abstinence at weeks 14 and 18^{NS} 	Not reported	Study rated as low quality due to poor conduct and reporting.

3 DISCUSSION

3.1 Summary of the findings

This rapid review aimed to identify the effectiveness of PHM in improving healthcare delivery, health outcomes and reducing inequalities. PHM is a multicomponent complex approach aimed at reducing health inequalities by identifying specific at-risk groups and utilising collaborative multi-agency working to implement specific interventions. Three studies were identified that evaluated the effectiveness of a PHM approach, and four studies were identified that examined the effectiveness of specific interventions using a PHM approach. The included studies incorporated a variety of different PHM components. Although the evidence appears promising, there was considerable heterogeneity among the interventions regarding their aims, target population groups and health outcomes, which made synthesis challenging. As a result, no conclusion can be made as to the overall effectiveness of PHM. This should be considered when developing or planning PHM interventions.

As previously noted, (and detailed in section 6.3), for this rapid review we used the six key components of PHM identified by Van Ede et al., (2023) to inform our eligibility criteria. Each component has three to five elements. The included studies rarely reported PHM components with sufficient clarity to allow us to determine which elements had or had not been incorporated. Therefore, it was necessary to make certain inferences about what aspects of their methodology could be interpreted as PHM approach. The most commonly reported elements were co-ordination and support structures; multistakeholder governance structures across the continuum of care; goals and objectives supported by resources; a cross domain and co-designing workforce; integrated data that follows the patient across the continuum of care; and evidence-based evaluation through the availability of population data. Whereas the least commonly reported elements included a group of stakeholders with financial arrangements; additional funding; financial incentives; investment and business plans to realise data infrastructure; community engagement; and strategies to maintain momentum (see section 7.4).

Three comparative studies evaluating the effectiveness of a PHM approach in improving health delivery, health outcomes, or reducing inequalities were identified. This included the implementation of prevention focused integrated care models, SDoH focused care model, and a community-based programme designed to improve care coordination and address clinical and social determinants of health. Four further studies were identified that evaluated the effectiveness of specific interventions targeting high risk groups and developed using a PHM approach, which included a SDoH screening and referral process in primary care, food supplementation intervention, person-centred smoking cessation intervention, and clinic-to-community physical activity referral intervention. In addition, it is important to note that no studies specifically evaluated the impact of PHM in terms of narrowing inequalities amongst the identified at risk groups, an important aim of PHM. However, the PHM or interventions evaluated within all the included studies had the potential of achieving the aim of reducing inequalities.

Findings from studies evaluating the PHM approach were mixed. The prevention focused integrated care models implemented across two sites led to increased costs of secondary care per patient per year and in costs per user of secondary care (Stokes et al., 2021). The integrated care model also led to a statistically significant increase in emergency admissions at one site. No effects were found on patients self-reported health status or patient experience (Stokes et al., 2021). However, there is evidence to suggest a SDoH focused care model can

lead to reduced ED visits, hospital admissions and costs per patient. Health-related quality of life and patient satisfaction were also found to increase (Sioni et al., 2025). The J-CHiP community-based programme led to mixed findings in terms of costs and healthcare utilisation in relation to patients' medical insurance payer type (Murphy et al., 2018).

Findings from studies evaluating the specific interventions designed using a PHM approach appear to be in favour of the intervention. The food supplementation intervention led to the successful provision of food supplementation, reduced emergency department visits and hospitalisations (Scher et al., 2022). The person-centred smoking cessation intervention led to increased quitline engagement, increased treatment engagement and increased abstinence (Hitsman et al., 2022). The clinic-to-community, physical activity referral intervention led to decreased body weight and systolic blood pressure. Those with hypertension were found to have decreased body weight, systolic and diastolic blood pressures. The revenue generated from the model was larger than the cost of scholarship provided to those in need of financial support (Porter et al., 2022). The social determinants of health screening and referral process intervention led to increased screening and referral amongst those who need it most (Ajibola et al., 2025).

Participants were generally accepting of the interventions, highlighting satisfaction with the interventions, the personnel involved, and describing multiple benefits of engaging. In one study that aimed to improve healthcare delivery, no differences in patient perceptions were found when compared to controls suggesting the intervention did not positively or negatively impact the patient experience.

The most applicable intervention to the Welsh context may be the study assessing the impact of integrated care models for high-risk patients (Stokes et al., 2021), as this study was conducted in the UK. The study included each key component of PHM and incorporated: a cross-domain business model; integrated data infrastructure; population data analytics and emergent implementation strategies. The findings suggest that integrated care models based on a PHM approach led to increased costs of secondary care per patient per year, and costs per user of secondary care and led to mixed findings for emergency admissions, with no significant differences in primary care utilisation (Stokes et al., 2021). This study also reported health-related quality of life outcome, with no significant differences between the intervention and control groups. This was the only study to compare patient experiences to a control group receiving usual care. This showed no overall differences in whether patients felt they had received enough support to manage their long-term health condition between those receiving usual care and those receiving integrated care. This suggests the integrated care models may not impact patients' sense of support in a positive or a negative way. However, as the evidence was from a single study, no firm conclusions can be drawn.

Overall, the evidence base was limited, with only seven studies being included in this rapid review. Due to the limited number of studies, the varied intervention types, the low quality of reporting, and the heterogeneity in outcomes resulting in most outcomes only being reported by a single study, the overall confidence in the findings is low and further evidence would be needed to draw any firm conclusions.

3.2 Strengths and limitations of the available evidence

Although limited studies examined the effectiveness of PHM, the available evidence suggests that a range of interventions incorporating aspects of PHM approaches may be effective at improving various health outcomes and reducing inequalities. However, the evidence also showed some mixed findings in relation to healthcare delivery, cost and healthcare utilisation depending on the population group, or their type of medical insurance.

The differing aims, populations, outcomes and the inconsistent reporting of PHM components across the interventions identified make it difficult to compare the overall effectiveness of interventions that incorporate components of PHM and limits the overall confidence of the evidence base. In addition, all the available evidence was deemed to be of low quality, and each outcome was reported by only one study per intervention grouping, which further reduces our overall confidence in the findings and suggests the results should be interpreted with caution.

Interventions utilising a PHM approach, as evidenced by the studies included in this review, can vary greatly. This can include broad approaches such as integrating whole care systems, or narrow approaches such as identifying a specific population group, identifying a specific health need and addressing that. This variation makes it difficult to directly compare the studies. As described previously, PHM includes several components, which can vary across the literature. All of our included studies incorporated some PHM components such as cross collaboration. However, this creates an additional challenge. In an ideal world, to evaluate the impact of a PHM approach, it would be useful to assess the effectiveness of each component, however, this may not be practical. As none of the included studies have described in detail, nor evaluated the effectiveness of the individual components, we can only rely on the findings reported for the individual interventions.

All of the included studies were aimed at disadvantaged or at-risk population groups such as high-need high-cost patients, high-risk patients with one or more chronic conditions, those who were considered inactive and/or had a chronic condition, those experiencing food insecurity, financial constraints, transportation access issues, low-income smokers. This suggests a need for caution when generalising the findings to broader populations.

Very few included studies considered any aspect of the PROGRESS-PLUS framework (see sections 6.8 and 7.5. Although all studies included disadvantaged or at-risk populations, they did not consider how socioeconomic factors, ethnicity, or social capital affect access and success of interventions incorporating PHM approaches.

Notably, a large proportion of the included studies (n=6) were conducted in the USA, many of which referenced private healthcare systems such as Medicaid and Medicare. This will undoubtedly limit the generalisability of the findings to the Welsh context. Furthermore, none of the included studies were longitudinal, which would be valuable for assessing the long-term impact of interventions which incorporated different aspects of PHM to varying degrees on patient outcomes and healthcare costs, offering insights into sustainability and overall effectiveness.

Lastly, another limitation emerging from evidence identified in this review is the limited number of studies assessing the economic impact of interventions incorporating various aspects of PHM. Economic evaluations are crucial for guiding policymakers and healthcare providers in resource allocation and scalability, particularly among interventions utilising a PHM approach,

which encompasses multi-sector collaboration. Without a clear understanding of cost-effectiveness, it remains challenging to determine whether the benefits of PHM outweigh their implementation and operational costs.

3.3 Strengths and limitations of this Rapid Review

An abbreviated systematic review methodology was used to conduct this rapid review in order to provide the available evidence in a timely manner whilst maintaining attention to bias. The studies included were identified using an extensive search of electronic databases with over 90% of search results being screened in duplicate. Quality appraisal of all included studies was also conducted independently, in duplicate with any disagreements resolved within the review team. Any data extracted from the included studies were consistency checked by a second reviewer. This rapid review systematically mapped all included studies against the components of PHM and the PROGRESS-PLUS framework, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of equity considerations and alignment with PHM principles.

As highlighted throughout this rapid review, PHM is complex, and often poorly or inconsistently defined within the literature. Therefore, we chose to only include studies that specifically stated they had used a PHM approach and met the inclusion criteria outlined in Table 3 and section 6.3. During an initial full text screening of 206 articles 55 studies were considered potentially relevant (used the term PHM). However, it became clear that the term PHM had been used inconsistently, and not all of the 55 studies described a PHM approach as defined by Van Ede et al (2023) and the Welsh Government PHM Task and Finish Group. As a result, and in order to try to limit inclusion to studies that evaluated a PHM that aligned with our interpretation and definitions of PHM, the rapid review focused on studies that emphasised cross collaboration as this component was identified as an important and underpinning aspect across the essential PHM components. This also ensured that the included approaches were in line with our definitions of PHM. After the second stage of full text screening, only seven studies met our revised inclusion criteria. However, this in turn means that the included studies may not fully capture all aspects of PHM and may overrepresent collaborative elements while underrepresenting other components and this selective approach may have resulted in missing relevant evidence. Therefore, it is likely that additional studies that incorporate some of the PHM components (but do not include cross collaboration initiatives), and have not been included in this review, may provide useful evidence for developing PHM interventions. In addition, as the review focused on the effectiveness of PHM in improving health delivery, health outcomes and reducing inequalities we only sought to include comparative studies. We did not look at implementation.

The majority of included studies focused on assessing the effectiveness of specific interventions targeting high risk groups, rather than evaluating the impact of PHM as a whole. None of the included studies measured the impact of other distinct PHM components such as integrated data infrastructure, co-designing workforce and community, and population data analytics, although where wider components of PHM were reported on in the paper, we have highlighted these.

3.4 Implications for policy and practice

The evidence demonstrates that PHM is a complex multicomponent approach that can be implemented in various ways and at different levels within the healthcare system, depending on population needs and priorities. However, the literature identified in this rapid review focused on evaluating the effectiveness of targeted interventions developed to address the identified needs, whilst the impact of the different PHM components was not measured, making it

challenging to determine the effectiveness of PHM approaches. Policy makers and practitioners should take this into account when designing PHM interventions, in order to allow for robust evaluations of the PHM components that have been utilised.

The majority of PHM interventions were delivered across multiple care settings, involving multiple collaborating partners and a range of personnel to deliver the interventions. This suggests interventions incorporating PHM require a considerable number of resources and planning, which may impact applicability and feasibility. However, it is encouraging to see the variety of interventions identified that incorporate a PHM approach and the different collaborating partners involved, suggesting that this approach has the potential of multiple applications.

PHM has the potential to improve healthcare outcomes and enhance healthcare delivery by enabling more targeted collaborative and pragmatic approaches. To realise this potential, policies should focus on addressing implementation challenges, ensuring comprehensive and high-quality data integration, and fostering collaboration across various sectors. Healthcare organisations need to evolve if they are to adopt PHM approaches, and investment in infrastructure and workforce capacity would appear to be essential.

Welsh Government are currently developing a policy document providing a clear understanding of PHM and how it can be implemented which will provide consistency across Wales and should be considered when developing any future PHM approaches.

3.5 Implications for future research

This rapid review has highlighted several implications for future research. While screening it became clear that the term PHM is inconsistently and poorly described within the literature, with many studies using the terms population health and PHM interchangeably. In addition, components of PHM were reported in varying degrees within the included studies. Therefore, studies using a PHM approach should clearly, and adequately describe which components were incorporated to enable replication. This would support direct comparisons between studies and allow for robust evaluation of the PHM.

A limited number of studies exploring the effectiveness of PHM approach or intervention in terms of healthcare delivery, health outcomes and reducing inequalities were identified. All included studies were deemed to be low quality and only one study was conducted in the UK. Therefore, further high-quality UK studies are needed to strengthen the evidence base and improve the overall confidence in the findings.

4 ECONOMIC CONSIDERATIONS

This section has been completed by the Centre for Health Economics & Medicines Evaluation (CHEME), Bangor University

- When estimated at the population-level across England, additional expenditure in public health generated quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) at a much lower cost per additional QALY [£3,800 per QALY] than additional NHS expenditure [£13,500 per QALY]. If £1billion were invested into both approaches, public health would generate 206,398 additional QALYs, compared to 67,060 QALYs generated by the NHS (Martin, Lomas & Claxton, 2020).
- There exists a paucity of economic evidence at the individual PHM-level. Therefore, economic evaluations of PHM may wish to consider changes in healthcare resource use and associated costs of implementing PHM alongside measures of effectiveness, such as in Stokes et al., 2021 included in this review.
- Consideration of healthcare resource use and the associated cost implications are particularly pertinent given high levels of resource intensity required to implement PHM and the variance in PHM components identified by this review.
- Economic evaluations of PHM can vary assumptions and key elements of analysis based on the possible different applications of PHM. Key elements of the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) economic evaluation reference case that can be varied to reflect different possible PHM interventions include:
 - **The perspective of analysis:** *NHS and social service perspective* to assess costs that fall on those sectors: *wider societal* to capture wider cost impacts such as employment, productivity or other non-health sector spillover effects.
 - **Time horizons:** Longer time horizons may be used when outcomes are expected to be realised over a longer time period, such as preventative interventions. Shorter time horizons should be used for interventions expected to achieve outcomes relatively quickly. NICE recommends a time horizon long enough to reflect and capture important differences in costs or outcomes).
 - **Discount rate:** For costs and outcomes that are expected to be realised in a period longer than one year, discounting of future outcomes is conducted to bring the values of outcomes in line with present values. Evaluations of interventions with outcomes expected to be realised rather distantly in the future (such as preventative interventions) may wish to vary the discount rate used as higher discount rates may undervalue the present value of outcomes arising further in the future).
- The NICE technology appraisal manual should be consulted to inform the development of economic evaluations of PHM interventions in the UK (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2025).

5 REFERENCES

Barker, T. H., Habibi, N., Aromataris, E., Stone, J. C., Leonardi-Bee, J., Sears, K., Hasanoff, S., Klugar, M., Tufanaru, C., Moola, S., & Munn, Z. (2024). The revised JBI critical appraisal tool for the assessment of risk of bias for quasi-experimental studies. *JBI evidence synthesis*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.11124/JBIES-23-00268>

Barker, T. H., Stone, J. C., Sears, K., Klugar, M., Tufanaru, C., Leonardi-Bee, J., Aromataris, E., & Munn, Z. (2023). The revised JBI critical appraisal tool for the assessment of risk of bias for randomized controlled trials. *JBI evidence synthesis*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.11124/JBIES-22-00430>

Cochrane methods. (2026). *PROGRESS-Plus*. Available at: [PROGRESS-Plus | Cochrane Equity](#)

Cwm Taf Morgannwg University Health Board. (no date). *Population Health and Population Health Management*. Available at: [Population Health and Population Health Management - Cwm Taf Morgannwg University Health Board](#)

Karran, E.L., Cashin, A.G., Barker, T., Boyd, M.A., Chiarotto, A., Dewidar, O., Mohabir, V., Petkovic, J., Sharma, S., Tejani, S. and Tugwell, P. (2023). Using PROGRESS-plus to identify current approaches to the collection and reporting of equity-relevant data: a scoping review. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2023.09.017>

Leatherdale, S. T. (2018). Natural experiment methodology for research: a review of how different methods can support real-world research. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2018.1488449>

Lenus: Research Repository. (2022). *Population Health Management: A Position Paper*. Available at: <https://www.lenus.ie/server/api/core/bitstreams/aff4e74c-566e-4d3d-a567-ae498f212856/content>

Martin, S., Lomas, J. and Claxton, K. (2020). Is an ounce of prevention worth a pound of cure? A cross-sectional study of the impact of English public health grant on mortality and morbidity. *BMJ open*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-036411>

McCann, L., Johnson, L., & Ford, J. (2023). Equity-focused evidence synthesis - A need to optimise our approach. *Public health in practice (Oxford, England)*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhip.2023.100430>

Moola S, Munn Z, Tufanaru C, Aromataris E, Sears K, Sfetcu R, Currie M, Qureshi R, Mattis P, Lisy K, Mu P-F. *Chapter 7: Systematic reviews of etiology and risk*. In: Aromataris E, Munn Z (Editors). *JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis*. JBI, 2020. Available at: <https://synthesismanual.jbi.global>

National Institute for Health and Care Excellence. (2025). *NICE technology appraisal and highly specialised technologies guidance: the manual*. Available at: <https://www.nice.org.uk/process/pmg36/chapter/economic-evaluation-2>

NHS Confederation. (2023). *Population health management: An introduction*. Available at: <https://www.nhsconfed.org/articles/population-health-management-introduction>

NHS England. (no date). *Reducing healthcare inequalities using population health management*. Available at: [NHS England » Reducing healthcare inequalities using population health management](#)

NHS England. (no date). *Integrated care systems: Population health management*. Available at: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/integratedcare/phm/>

Oliver, S., Kavanagh, J., Caird, J., Lorenc, T., Oliver, K., Harden, A., Thomas, J., Greaves, A. and Oakley, A. (2008). Health promotion, inequalities and young people's health: a systematic review of research. *EPPI-Centre, London*. Available at: <https://researchonline.lshtm.ac.uk/id/eprint/4646468>

Swarthout, M. & Bishop, M.A. (2017). Population health management: Review of concepts and definitions. *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2146/ajhp170025>

Van Ede, A. F., Minderhout, R. N., Stein, K. V., & Bruijnzeels, M. A. (2023). How to successfully implement population health management: a scoping review. *BMC Health Services Research*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-023-09915-5>

Weightman A, Lifford K, Mann M, et al. (2022). A rapid review of what is known about the effectiveness of strategies to address challenging and disruptive behaviours in students in a classroom setting. *Health and Care Research Wales*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.35542/osf.io/u57ac>

WHO. (2023). *Population health management in primary health care: a proactive approach to improve health and well-being*. Available at: [WHO-EURO-2023-7497-47264-69316-eng.pdf](#)

6 RAPID REVIEW METHODS

6.1 Eligibility criteria

Searches for primary sources were conducted to answer the review question:

What is the effectiveness of population health management in improving healthcare delivery, health outcomes and reducing inequalities?

Table 3. Eligibility criteria

	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Participants	Any defined population	General population
Settings	All settings	n/a
Intervention / exposure	Studies evaluating population health management (PHM) or any intervention explicitly stated as utilising a PHM approach A post hoc decision was made to further exclude studies that did not comply with our agreed definition of PHM (this is outlined in more detail in Section 6.3)	
Comparison	Any comparator	No comparator
Outcomes	Effectiveness outcomes (including, healthcare delivery, health outcomes, health inequalities/equity, cost-effectiveness)	
Study design	Comparative studies, economic evaluations	Case studies, cross-sectional studies and qualitative studies, any type of evidence synthesis
Countries	Any	
Language of publication	English	Non-English
Publication date	No date limit	
Publication type	Published and preprint journal articles, published reports.	Commentaries, conference abstracts, books, editorials, letters, literature reviews, dissertations and theses
Other factors <i>Any other key points to note</i>	Although any countries will be eligible for inclusion, stakeholders have a particular interest in UK studies.	

6.2 Literature search

A search was conducted of the electronic bibliographic databases: Medline, Embase and Scopus. The search strategy used for Medline is available in Appendix 2. A search for grey

literature was conducted in The Health Foundation website and The King's Fund Library database. A Google search for NHS produced grey literature was also conducted. Reports of primary studies identified in the scoping stage of this review were also cross-checked and included with all other search results if unique. All searches were conducted on 29th September 2025. The searches were focused on the phrase 'population health management'. Term analysis of relevant primary evidence identified in the scoping searches, showed that only this phrase was used consistently as a free text term in the titles and abstracts or as an indexed term in relation to this topic area. The searches were limited to records published in the English language.

6.3 Study selection process

Following removal of duplicates in Endnote 20, all articles were imported to a systematic reviewing software Rayyan for screening. For title and abstract screening, titles were screened by a single reviewer against the eligibility criteria in section 6.1 (Table 3). To ensure consistency, over 90% of studies were screened by two independent reviewers. Full text screening was carried out in duplicate by two independent reviewers, and any conflicts were discussed and resolved within the team.

A two-stage full-text screening process was used. An initial screening of the papers retrieved as full-text identified 55 papers that used the term PHM. However, upon reviewing these papers in more detail, we observed inconsistencies in how PHM was conceptualised. Overall, the literature presented a very unclear and complex picture of what PHM is, and it was evident that no consensus exists on a clear definition or conceptualisation. Considering the Welsh Government definition of PHM provided by stakeholders (summarised in section 1.2), alongside the six essential components of PHM identified within the scoping review by Van Ede et al. (2023), we identified that using a *collaborative approach* was a common component across both descriptors. This feature encompasses the use of linked datasets, breaking down silos, fostering collaboration across data sharing, and intervention design, and implementation, with the aim of reducing health inequalities. Therefore, we decided to prioritise papers that incorporated a collaborative approach. Based on this additional eligibility criterion, a second stage screen of the 55 papers was conducted, to identify papers that reported on a PHM approach that incorporated a collaborative component for inclusion in our rapid review. Details of the studies excluded at the second stage full-text screening and the reason why are presented in Section 9 (Appendix 1)

6.4 Data extraction

Data was extracted directly from the primary studies by one reviewer, and a second reviewer consistency checked the data extracted for accuracy and completeness. The information extracted included:

- Reference (author, year, country)
- Source
- Study design
- Study aim
- Participant characteristics (e.g. target population; number of participants; health condition)
- Intervention details (Population Health Management approach utilised)
- Health care delivery or treatment used
- Comparators
- Outcomes measured
- Key findings (did PHM improve the overall treatment provision and ultimate health outcomes)

- Reviewer comments

6.5 Study design classification

The studies were classified based on the authors' descriptions.

6.6 Quality appraisal

Quality assessment was undertaken by two independent reviewers, with any discrepancies discussed and resolved within the team. The JBI critical appraisal checklists for quasi-experimental studies (Barker et al., 2024), RCTs (Barker et al., 2023) and cohort studies (Moola et al., 2020) were used to assess the methodological quality of each included study. The findings of the quality appraisal for each study can be seen in section 7.3.

For the purposes of this rapid review, a pragmatic system devised and used in a previous rapid review (Weightman et al., 2022), was used to assess each study as being of high, moderate, or low quality. The criteria for these are:

High quality: RCT plus a score of 8 or more YES on the JBI RCT check list, plus, no concerns suggesting a medium or high risk of bias in any aspect of the study design.

Moderate quality: RCT plus a score of 6 or more YES on the JBI RCT check list OR a score of 8 or more YES on the JBI quasi-experimental study checklist, plus, no concerns suggesting a very high risk of bias in any aspect of the study design.

Low quality: Others

6.7 Synthesis

Due to the heterogeneity of the evidence base, data was synthesised narratively to provide an interpretation of the evidence.

6.8 PROGRESS-PLUS mapping

PROGRESS-PLUS is a framework endorsed by the Cochrane Collaboration to assist with the identification and classification of health equity within systematic reviews (McCann et al., 2023 and Karran et al., 2023). It is useful in assisting the identification of participant characteristics that stratify health opportunities and outcomes (Cochrane methods, 2026). PROGRESS-PLUS considers a range of characteristics that can impact health. PROGRESS refers to the place of residence; race/ethnicity/culture/language; occupation; gender; religion; education; socioeconomic status, and social capital. PLUS refers to additional context-specific personal characteristics that may contribute to health inequalities and incorporate features of relationships and time-dependent relationships (Cochrane methods, 2026 and Karran et al., 2023).

All the included studies were mapped against PROGRESS-PLUS, the findings of which are presented in section 7.5. During the mapping process we recorded where any study had provided a further sub-group analysis for any other additional characteristics that may provide evidence for any impacts on health inequalities. The details of the included population groups can be found in table 9.

6.9 Assessment of body of evidence

To assess the overall body of evidence considerations were made based on the study designs, quality of the evidence, and the direction of effect. This information is provided for the differing interventions in Table 2.

7 EVIDENCE

7.1 Search results and study selection

A visual representation of the flow of studies throughout the review can be found in Figure 1. A total of 2,514 records were retrieved via the searches and 1,089 records remained following deduplication. Two hundred and six articles were screened during the first stage of full text screening to identify studies that stated they were using PHM. This resulted in 55 studies being screened during the second stage of full text screening to ensure that their approaches were in line with our definition of PHM (and included a collaborative component). The two-stage full text screening process resulted in a final set of seven studies for inclusion in our rapid review.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

7.2 Data extraction

Table 4. Summary of included studies

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/ notes
<p>Ajibola et al., (2025). Identifying and addressing social determinants of health with an electronic health record. <i>The Journal of the American Board of Family Medicine</i>, 38(1), 9-14.</p> <p>(USA)</p>	<p>Study design: Repeated measures study</p> <p>Aim: To examine how leveraging an Electronic Health Record (EHR) system can facilitate Social Determinants of Health (SDoH) screening and its integration into Primary Care.</p> <p>Collaboration: FindHelp.org worked with leadership and care management teams from three primary care sites to create and streamline a process for patients who provided positive responses to SDoH surveys. Co-designing and refining screening questions with patients and improving screening process by consolidating SDoH questions into an EPIC rooming tab in the Electronic Health Record (EHR).</p> <p>Dates of data collection: 2020-2023 Phase 1 (2020 to 2021) Phase 2 (Mid-2021 to Dec 2022) Phase 3 (Jan 2023 to 2024)</p> <p>Data collection methods: A Social Determinants of Health (SDoH) screening questionnaire was used to identify people who would benefit from a referral.</p>	<p>Sample size: n=35,105 (in 2020); n=41,874 (in 2021); n=42,335 (in 2022).</p> <p>Target population: Patients experiencing food insecurity, financial constraints, and transportation issues.</p> <p>Health condition(s): none specified</p> <p>Setting: 3 medical primary care Sites (of Star Community Health in the Lehigh Valley district, USA), remote and community based.</p> <p>Intervention details (Population Health Management approach utilised): The intervention was executed in 3 phases for continuous refinement.</p> <p>Phase 1 (2020 to 2021) In the first phase, using predesigned questions from an EPIC Healthy Planet—a population health management module from the EPIC system an SDoH questionnaire was generated and integrated into the patient Electronic Health Record (EHR). The FindHelp.org website serves as an endpoint in the referral pipeline, where users can be connected to local resources such as food, housing, and financial assistance.</p> <p>Phase 2 (Mid 2021 to Dec 2022) In the second phase, the Community Needs Assessment tool was used to streamline the screening process by selecting the top 3 needs in the patient population: food insecurity, financial constraints, and transportation access. To further simplify the process, these questions—previously scattered in the HER were consolidated into an EPIC rooming tab and integrated into the rooming procedure. Medical assistants (MAs), licensed practical nurses (LPNs), and</p>	<p>Primary findings: In 2020, out of 35,105 patients seen at the centre, 39% were screened for SDoH. Out of the 13,704 patients screened, 24% had positive screening results. In 2021, out of the 41,874 patients seen at the centre, 51% were screened for SDoH. Out of the 21,167 patients screened, 18% had positive screening results. In 2022, out of the 42,335 patients seen, 76% were screened for SDoH. Out of 32,268 patients screened, 15% received a positive screening result. (2,623 patients reported financial hardship, 1,390 patients confirmed food insecurity and 967 patients reported transportation issues).</p> <p>SDoH screening increased by 95% from 2020 to 2022 with a consequent increase in social work referrals and the allocation of resources to a targeted patient population.</p> <p>SDoH screening was increased from 39% in 2020 to 76% in 2022—a 95% increase over 3 years. While there was an increase in the number of patients that were screened, it is important to note that there was a decrease in the percentage of positive patients that were captured. However, despite the percentage decrease, there was an increase in the absolute number of positive screenings.</p> <p>Additional findings: Strategy and training were the primary drivers of the increase in screening.</p>	<p>Although the 2023 data collection was not complete, referrals to social work increased from 375 to 2,226 in 2023—nearly a fivefold increase. Inconsistency is observed in reporting the phase period. In the methods section, phase 3 is described between Jan 2023 to 2024, while in the results section, it says, “Following Phase 3 implementation in 2022,” This creates confusion about when Phase 3 actually started.</p>

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/ notes
	<p>The screening questions were adjusted in phase 2 for the specific needs of the primary care practice cluster. If a patient responded positively, it triggered an automated social work referral, and the result was entered into a database specific to the patient's SDoH needs. In phase 3 patients were first asked if they would like a social work consult before referral. Information about how many people actually connected with programmes was taken from FindHelp.org.</p> <p>Data Shared/integrated: Screening questions on SDoH were integrated into a patient's Electronic Health Record (EHR). Responses were entered into the EHR. Referral results were entered into a database specific to the patient's SDoH needs. Separate FindHelp.org links were integrated into the Electron Health Record (EHR). Data was tracked across the 3 medical primary care sites. Staff also collected data to measure the use of FindHelp.org.</p> <p>Outcomes: Number of patients screened; number of positive screening results; number of FindHelp.org users, and number of people being connected with programmes.</p> <p>Quality rating: Low quality</p>	<p>registered nurses (RNs) asked patients the questions and entered responses into the EHR. If a patient responded positively to one or more of these domains, a Best Practice Advisory (BPA) pop-up screen was triggered. The BPA in this phase automated a social work referral, and the result was entered into a database specific to the patient's SDoH needs.</p> <p>Phase 3 (Jan 2023 to 2024)</p> <p>In the third phase, automated referrals were revised and the patient was first asked if they would like a social work consult. If the patient agreed, a referral was sent and signed by the clinicians during the encounter. Two separate FindHelp.org links were integrated into EPIC, making them easily accessible to both staff in the EHR and to patients on their MyChart platform—a secure online portal that allows patients to access their personal health information and communicate with their health care clinicians. The network's case management and community outreach manager continued to work on engaging the community to be able to track how many referrals resulted in resource allocation. In addition, staff were trained to navigate the FindHelp.org resource page and monitor patients who use the community services.</p> <p>Healthcare delivery or treatment used: Social Determinants of Health (SDoH) screening and referrals to community services.</p> <p>Comparator: Different intervention years (2020, 2021, and 2022).</p>	<p>In 2020, there were only 111 users for the FindHelp.org website, and 16 of them were connected with programmes. The user count rose to 2,283 in 2021, with 178 patients being connected to a program, and 3,888 in 2022, with 977 being connected to a program. In that time, 25.27% of the searches were related to housing, and 22% were related to food. Following Phase 3 implementation in 2022, ambulatory referrals to social work totaled 375, including 12 from FindHelp.org. During that time, 97% of the social work referrals made contact with the patients to directly address their positive screen.</p>	
Hitsman et al., (2022). An EHR-	Study design: Two-group, pilot randomised controlled study	Sample size: n=190 (PHM intervention n=97; control group n=93).	Primary findings:	

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/ notes
<p>automated and theory-based population health management intervention for smoking cessation in diverse low-income patients of safety-net health centers: a pilot randomized controlled trial. <i>Translational behavioral medicine</i>, 12(9), pp.892-899 ,</p> <p>(USA)</p>	<p>Aim: This study evaluated the effectiveness of a person-centered and EHR-automated population health management (PHM) intervention for smoking cessation that was embedded in a community health centre primary care setting and designed to engage low-income smokers outside of the primary care visit.</p> <p>Collaboration: Bidirectional e-referral between EHR and Illinois Tobacco Quitline (ITQL), supported by Alliance- Chicago. The text messaging component of the PHM intervention was automated by TouchPointCare, a telehealth system service provider.</p> <p>Dates of data collection: April 2017 to Sep 2019</p> <p>Data collection methods: A telephone interview was used to conduct baseline assessments. Data on smoking cessation for PHM and EUC participants and smoking cessation treatment (non-quitline) utilization for EUC participants were obtained as a part of the longitudinal observational study. Quitline engagement, utilization, and smoking cessation outcomes were transmitted directly from the ITQL server to the EHR system and were obtained via the NNHSC EHR system.</p>	<p>Target population: Diverse low-income patients who were ≥18 years old, identified as a “current someday smoker” or “current everyday smoker” in the EHR and had ≥1 provider visits within the past 12 months.</p> <p>Health condition(s): none specified</p> <p>Setting: Remote, community-based</p> <p>Intervention details (Population Health Management approach utilised): The PHM intervention comprised three components: (i) proactive e-referral to the quitline; (ii) a single-page letter developed through patient focus groups, guided by SDT, and printed via the EHR system; and (iii) five text messages that reinforced the central messaging of the letter. The letter and text messages were developed in English and Spanish and delivered according to the patient’s preferred language for health care as identified in the EHR. The letter was sent on behalf of the director of performance improvement and primary care provider at NNHSC and addressed low motivation by encouraging either smoking cessation or reduction as an initial step to cessation. The letter also provided information about treatment, including the safety and effectiveness of nicotine replacement therapy (NRT), and stated that a quitline counsellor would be calling within 2 weeks to offer free treatment. The central message developed through focus groups was “Choose to change and make your own goals.” The letter also contained other elements of SDT designed to increase autonomous motivation (e.g., provided autonomy support through minimizing pressure and control) and standard supportive and motivational statements to encourage behaviour change. The letter was designed for smokers with low health literacy. The written message was one page in length to minimize cognitive overload and burden and to maximize</p>	<p>Participants (N = 190; 64.7% women, 82.1% African American/Black, 8.4% Hispanic/Latino). Due to project timeline constraints, only the first 96 participants were followed for 32 weeks.</p> <p>Participant screening, accrual, and retention in the observational study: Of the 1606 patients who were identified via the EHR system and contacted, 387 (24.0%) completed the eligibility screen, and 190 (11.8%) enrolled, completed the baseline assessment, and were randomised in the pilot clinical trial to the PHM intervention. Of the participants screened, 96.9% (375/387) owned a cell phone with texting capability. Survey completion rates at weeks 6, 14, and 28 after randomisation and letter mailing (10, 18, and 32 weeks after the baseline assessment) were comparably high between arms. Due to project timeline constraints, only the first 96 participants were followed for 32 weeks.</p> <p>Effects of intervention on treatment engagement, utilization, and smoking cessation: None of the PHM intervention participants opted out of the proactive quitline call and 8.2% (8/97) opted out of text messaging. By week 6, no EUC participants (0/92) and 25.8% (25/97) of PHM participants had engaged in quitline treatment (OR = 0, 95% CI: 0 to 0.13, p < .0001). No additional PHM participants engaged in treatment after week 6. Of the 25 PHM participants who engaged in quitline treatment, 44.0% were women, 80.0% were African American/Black, and 12.0% were Hispanic/Latino. By week 14, no EUC participants (0/92) and 21.6% (21/97) of PHM participants were treatment utilisers (OR = 0, 95% CI: 0 to 0.17, p < .0001). At week 6, 4.3% (4/93) of</p>	

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/notes
	<p>Data shared/integrated: A signed order fired within the EHR system triggered an outbound referral request through the interface engine (Qvera). The outbound e-referral order request was confirmed via an automated review of a valid email address through Qvera, confirming the bidirectional connection between the EHR system and the ITQL. Once this process was completed, the outbound message was sent via an automated secure file transfer procedure to the ITQL and was received in less than 24hr. Within 24hr after each quitline session, a Health Level 7 (HL7) file was automatically produced that provided a summary update of the services performed and the information documented during the call. Again, Qvera confirmed the email address and connection, and the HL7 message was sent via secure file transfer to Alliance-Chicago where it automatically populated structured EHR fields. A summary document within the EHR was sent simultaneously to the patient's primary care provider to communicate the referral outcome. All information received from the ITQL was documented within the patient's EHR, allowing for a longitudinal view of treatment utilization and smoking status.</p> <p>Outcomes: Primary outcomes: Quitline engagement at 6 weeks (defined as accepting the first proactive call from the quitline</p>	<p>the message's effectiveness. The estimated readability according to the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level rating was 4.8 (fifth grade). Patients were asked to contact the NNHSC care coordinator if they did not want to be contacted by the quitline. Opt-outs and reasons for not participating were recorded. Five text messages were sent on days 1, 5, 8, 11, and 20 after letter mailing. The first message was: "From Near North Health Service: Look for a letter in the mail from your doctor about FREE services to help you cut down or quit smoking. You have choices!" The message sent on day 5 directed participants to view the mailed letter via a hyperlink. Text messages 2–5 included a simple opt-out of future messages with varying responses to opting out. Opt-outs were recorded. Health care delivery and access barriers were addressed through an EHR system that automated the identification of smokers, the printing of targeted intervention material, referral for proactive quitline treatment, and the return of treatment outcomes to the EHR system to support follow-up care.</p> <p>Healthcare delivery or treatment used: Smoking cessation services (Quitline, NRT and behavioural counselling sessions)</p> <p>Comparator: Participants assigned to the control condition were e-referred to the ITQ. If the patient was seen in the health centre for a routine evaluation or an acute problem, a medical assistant confirmed current smoking and advised the participant to quit using clear and strong language. Current smoking and advice to quit were documented in the EHR system by the medical assistant. Next, the participant was seen by the physician who addressed the purpose of the visit. An e-referral was made if the physician also discussed the patient's smoking, determined that the patient was willing to set a quit date in the next month, and the patient agreed to the referral.</p>	<p>EUC participants and 2.1% (2/97) of PHM participants were abstinent (OR = 2.13, 95% CI: 0.30 to 24.05, p = .437). At week 14, 3.2% (3/93) of EUC participants and 9.3% (9/97) of PHM participants were abstinent (OR = 0.33, 95% CI: 0.06 to 1.37, p = .134). At week 28, the primary endpoint, 6.4% (3/47) of EUC participants, and 16.3% (8/49) of PHM participants were abstinent (OR = 0.35, 95% CI: 0.06 to 1.60, p = .199).</p> <p>Quitline utilization among PHM intervention participants Among the 25 PHM participants who engaged in quitline treatment, all received cessation-focused behavioural counselling and 92% (23/25) received NRT. Of the participants who received NRT, 14 used the patch, 5 used gum, 3 used lozenge, and 1 used lozenge and gum. On average, PHM participants completed 4.0 (SD = 2.9) behavioural counselling sessions across 23.0 (SD = 17.0) days. The average duration of NRT use was 3.4 (SD = 2.3) weeks.</p> <p>Non-quitline smoking cessation treatment reported by EUC participants: During the 32-week observation period, 4 EUC participants reported receiving smoking cessation counselling and 20 participants reported using NRT. Additional smoking cessation treatment reported by EUC participants included: varenicline or bupropion (n = 7); mobile app (n = 1); text messaging program (n = 1); web-based program (n = 5); books, pamphlets, or other written material (n = 10); or alternative therapy, such as acupuncture, meditation, herbal supplements, vitamins, yoga, or massage therapy (n = 5).</p>	

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	<p>counselor, enrolling in treatment, and completing the first behavioral counseling session). Quitline treatment utilization at 14 weeks (defined as completing one or more additional behavioral counselling sessions by week 14), Smoking cessation at 28 weeks (defined as self-reported abstinence for at least 7 days before the week 28 assessment. Participants were classified as smoking if they reported smoking or could not be reached to provide data).</p> <p>Quality rating: Low quality</p>			
<p>Murphy et al., (2018). Going beyond clinical care to reduce health care spending: findings from the J-CHiP community-based population health management program evaluation. Medical care, 56(7), 603-609.</p> <p>(USA)</p>	<p>Study design: Non-randomised controlled trial</p> <p>Aim: To report the impact of a community-based population health management program on cost and utilization from 2011 to 2016.</p> <p>Collaboration: The Johns Hopkins Community Health Partnership (J-CHiP) was created as a regional approach to health care transformation in Maryland, USA. J-CHiP deployed a comprehensive set of care coordination programmes across the continuum of traditional, and non-traditional, health care settings. One of the main components of J-CHiP was the community-based population health management program for high risk, chronically ill Medicaid and Medicare</p>	<p>Sample size: n=3,268 (intervention group: n=699 Medicaid, n=935 Medicare; control group: n=699 Medicaid, n=935 Medicare)</p> <p>Target population: High risk chronically ill adults (age 18+) Medicaid and Medicare beneficiaries, identified based on their risk of future hospitalisation, as indicated by predictive modelling, or through physician referral.</p> <p>Health condition(s): Any chronic condition, such as depression, bipolar, anxiety, obesity, or substance abuse issues.</p> <p>Setting: 8 primary care sites (throughout East Baltimore, Maryland, USA), other healthcare settings and the community.</p> <p>Intervention details (Population Health Management approach utilised): The program, embedded within 8 primary care sites throughout East Baltimore, was designed to improve care coordination and address the clinical and social</p>	<p>Primary findings: For Medicaid participants, costs were almost \$1200 per member per year lower for participants as a whole, Costs were \$2000 per member per year lower for those with a Health Behaviour Specialist, and \$3000 lower for those with a Care Manager; hospital admission and readmission rates were 9%–26% lower for those with a Care Manager and/or Health Behaviour Specialist. For Medicare participants, costs were lower (–\$476), but utilisation was similar or higher than non-participants. None of the observed Medicaid or Medicare differences were statistically significant.</p> <p>Costs: Costs increased for both groups from the pre to post periods, but the increases were generally smaller for J-CHiP participants. For the full Medicaid cohort, J-CHiP participants experienced a cost increase of \$2536 per member per year (PMPY), while comparison costs increase by \$3706 PMPY. This</p>	<p>‘The intervention augmented care management with programmes designed to address barriers to health experienced by the East Baltimore community surrounding Johns Hopkins Hospital and Johns Hopkins Bayview Medical Centre. This urban, underserved area has an average life expectancy as much as 20 years shorter than other more affluent, nearby neighbourhoods, reflecting</p>

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	<p>beneficiaries. The program, embedded within 8 primary care sites, was designed to improve care coordination and address the clinical and social determinants of health. At each site, multidisciplinary care coordination teams were formed with primary care providers, care managers (CM), health behavior specialists (HBS), and community health workers, as well as neighborhood navigators for residents in designated neighborhoods.</p> <p>Dates of data collection: 2011-2016</p> <p>Data collection methods: Data was collected using health plan enrolment data, claims, program records, Johns Hopkins Adjusted Clinical Groups (ACG) risk data, and predictive risk scores covering the period from December 2011 through March 2016. The primary predictor variables include indicators for group (J-CHiP vs. comparison) and study period (pre vs. post). The claims-based outcomes include counts of ED visits, inpatient admissions, and 30-day all cause readmissions, as well as paid costs, per member per year (PMPY). For Medicaid, both medical and pharmacy costs are included. For Medicare, costs are limited to medical claims due to the lack of timely pharmacy claims data. To measure the additive effect of the CM and HBS components, 2</p>	<p>determinants of health. At each site, multidisciplinary care coordination teams were formed. For those with chronic medical needs, the role of the site embedded Care Managers was to provide care coordination. This reduces unnecessary and avoidable utilisation, while ensuring that proper care is delivered at the most appropriate time and place. Participants with depression, bipolar, anxiety, obesity, or substance abuse issues were referred to site-embedded Health Behaviour Specialists (HBS). HBSs determined patients' mental health and emotional needs, developed treatment plans, delivered disease specific, protocol-based interventions, and provided referrals for psychiatric and pharmacological treatment when needed. Chronically ill adult (age 18+) participants were identified based on their risk of future hospitalization, as indicated by predictive modeling, or through physician referral. All eligible program participants were outreached by community health workers to engage and assess clinical and social needs. Those with complex medical or behavioral health needs were referred to CMs and/or HBSs, respectively. Participants residing in select East Baltimore neighborhoods may have also received assistance with social support and linkage to community services by a neighborhood navigator.</p> <p>Healthcare delivery or treatment used: Care co-ordination teams</p> <p>Comparator: The comparison group is identified from a pool of similar Medicaid and Medicare members who received primary care from any other nonintervention site.</p>	<p>represents a cost savings of \$1171 PMPY, although the difference is not statistically significant (difference=-\$1171 PMPY, 95% CI=-\$4968 to \$2145). A similar trend was found for Medicare beneficiaries, but the magnitude of the difference between groups (-\$476 PMPY, 95% CI=-\$4148 to \$3024) was smaller than found for Medicaid.</p> <p>Sub-analysis: CM and HBS cohort The comparative analysis results for the CM and HBS cohorts vary by payer. For the CM cohort, both payers demonstrated cost savings for J-CHiP participants (-\$3051 PMPY for Medicaid and -\$246 PMPY for Medicare), although the differences are not statistically significant. For Medicaid, the estimated savings for the CM cohort was more than double that of the full cohort (-\$3051 vs. -\$1171 PMPY, respectively), while the opposite was found for Medicare (-\$246 PMPY for CM vs. -\$476 for full). The HBS cohort also exhibited non-significant savings for Medicaid (-\$2038 PMPY) but not for Medicare where J-CHiP participant costs increased more than nonparticipants (+\$1980 PMPY).</p> <p>ED visits: The impact of J-CHiP on the number of ED visits is relatively small and mixed. For the full cohort of J-CHiP participants, the ratio of incident rate ratios (IRRs) demonstrates a small improvement over the comparison group for Medicaid (ratio=0.97), and slightly worse results for Medicare (ratio=1.02), although neither difference is statistically significant.</p> <p>Sub-analysis: CM and HBS cohort</p>	<p>higher rates of medical and psychosocial risk factors (e.g., prevalence of cardiovascular disease, infant mortality, substance use, mental illness).' 'Integration of behavioural health did not appear to improve results more than traditional CM, particularly for Medicare. The poor Medicare findings may be partly an artifact of the dataset which, by Centres for Medicare & Medicaid Services regulation, did not include Medicare claims data with substance abuse diagnoses. Without this data, it was difficult to measure the full impact of the HBS, particularly considering the high comorbidity of mental health conditions with substance abuse.'</p>

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	<p>additional cohorts are identified. In addition to the community health worker outreach and assessment services offered to the full cohort, participants in the CM and HBS cohorts received more intensive intervention services. The CM cohort includes a subset of J-CHiP participants who received case management assistance by a CM for at least 3 months. The HBS cohort is limited to J-CHiP participants with a mental or behavioural health condition who had at least 1 contact with an HBS. Inclusion of these cohorts helps measure the differential impact of J-CHiP for those who received more intensive intervention services as compared with the full cohort under the intention-to-treat design.</p> <p>Data shared/integrated: The evaluation uses health plan enrollment data, claims, program records, Johns Hopkins Adjusted Clinical Groups (ACG) risk data, and predictive risk scores covering the period from December 2011 through March 2016. The evaluation dataset includes 2–4 yearly measures per participant corresponding to the year before and up to 3 years after program implementation.</p> <p>Outcomes: Costs; emergency department visits; admissions; and readmissions.</p>		<p>For the CM cohort, both payers exhibited similar results for participants and nonparticipants (ratio=0.99). For the HBS cohort, the IRRs increased more for participants than nonparticipants (ratio=1.08 for Medicaid and 1.09 for Medicare), although the increases were not statistically significant.</p> <p>Admissions: The rate for the full Medicaid cohort was relatively unchanged (ratio=1.01).</p> <p>Sub-analysis: CM and HBS cohort The analysis showed a nonsignificant decrease in the admission rate for J-CHiP Medicaid participants in the CM and HBS cohorts (ratio of IRRs=0.91 for CM and 0.92 for HBS). For Medicare, all 3 cohorts showed an increase in the admission rate for J-CHiP participants as compared with nonparticipants (ratio=1.08 for full and 1.09 for CM), and the increase for the HBS cohort was statistically significant (ratio=1.28, 95% CI=1.01–1.65).</p> <p>Readmissions: readmission rates varied by payer.</p> <p>Sub-analysis: CM and HBS cohort For Medicaid, the CM and HBS cohorts showed nonsignificant improvements in the number of readmissions (ratio of IRRs = 0.84 for CM and 0.74 for HBS), although the full cohort did not experience the same improvement (ratio of IRRs= 1.03). For Medicare, all 3 cohorts exhibited increases in the readmission rate that were larger than the changes for the comparison group (ratio = 1.29 for full and CM, and 1.24 for HBS), although none were statistically significant.</p>	

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	<p>Quality rating: Low quality</p>		<p>Additional findings: The per member per year cost savings rate was even greater for participants who received more intensive intervention services, particularly those working with a Care Manager for at least 3 months. After accounting for implementation costs, these results reflect a return on investment (ROI) ranging from -2% (approximately the break-even point) for the full cohort to 154% for the subset that received more intensive services with a Care Manager.</p>	
<p>Porter et al., (2022). Design and implementation of a clinic-to-community, physical activity health promotion model for healthcare providers. <i>Preventive medicine reports</i>, 26, 101697.</p> <p>(USA)</p>	<p>Study design: Uncontrolled before and after study</p> <p>Aim: To describe the design and implementation of The Exercise is Medicine Greenville model (EIMG®), and provide observations for patient referral rates, retention rates, and satisfaction from 2016 to 2019, as well as limited effectiveness observations for associated changes in body weight, systolic and diastolic blood pressure.</p> <p>Collaboration: The University of South Carolina School of Medicine Greenville, Prisma Health, and YMCA of Greenville leveraged a multi-organisational partnership.</p> <p>Dates of data collection: 2016-2019</p> <p>Data collection methods: All physical activity (PA) program sessions, patient progress, and pre-post metrics are tracked using REDCap™ (Research Electronic Data Capture).</p>	<p>Sample size: n=347 (those who completed the programme: n=210)</p> <p>Target population: Patients ≥ 18 years of age, physically inactive (<150 min/week of moderate intensity aerobic activity) and/or have a chronic condition (i.e., overweight/obesity, hypertension, type 2 diabetes, stable heart disease).</p> <p>Health condition(s): Patients diagnosed with physical inactivity and/or noncommunicable disease.</p> <p>Setting: Clinic to community</p> <p>Intervention details (Population Health Management approach utilised): The EIMG® model was designed, implemented, launched at Prisma Health in Greenville, SC as a pilot in 2016 with the onboarding of 2 pilot clinics (1 internal medicine and 1 family medicine), and continually refined and scaled to 18 participating clinics (12 primary care and 6 specialty clinics; i.e. cancer survivorship and endocrinology) and considered at maturity (i.e. all components implemented) in 2018–2019. The EIMG® model connects patients referred by their healthcare provider to community partners who provide evidence-based physical activity</p>	<p>Primary findings: Since 2016, 973 patients were referred to the EIMG® team, 347 chose to enrol and 210 completed the programme.</p> <p>Biometric measurements 2016-2019 - Although outcomes cannot be determined as causal per se, adding EIMG® program participation to usual care was associated with a modest but statistically significant decrease in body weight (pre 102.5kg vs post 100.9kg; p<0.001) and systolic blood pressure (pre 128mmHg vs 126mmHg; p=0.042) with no significant decrease in resting heart rate (pre 76bpm vs post 76bpm; p=0.916) or diastolic blood pressure (pre 81mmHg vs post 80mmHg; p=0.137).</p> <p>Sub-analysis: Patients with hypertension Adding EIMG® program participation to usual care for patients with hypertension at time of referral was associated with a loss in body weight (pre 105.4kg vs post 104kg; p=0.001) and decreased systolic (pre 136mmHg vs post 129mmHg; p<0.001) and diastolic blood pressure (pre 86mmHg vs post 83mmHg; p<0.001), with no significant change in resting heart rate (pre 77bpm vs post 77bpm; p=0.572).</p>	<p>Limited effectiveness observations</p>

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	<p>a cloud-based, HIPAA-compliant software program. An exit survey was used to collect patient satisfaction. The survey included multiple questions addressing the satisfaction with the EIMG® program, HCP, EIMG® Coordinator, and EIMG® Pro, as well as demographic information. Amount of scholarship used, and revenue gained for each year were documented to demonstrate the financial support provided to patients with challenged economic stability, as well as the growth and sustainability of the program for patients who are financially stable to pay. Biometric data collection was performed (body weight, blood pressure, and resting heart rate) at the orientation visit and on the last visit (i.e. program completion). Weight was collected in duplicate while the patient was not wearing shoes utilizing a calibrated digital scale. Blood pressure and resting heart rate were measured in triplicate with the patient in a resting state (seated in a relaxed position; chair with a backrest and feet flat on the floor; minimum of 10 min) utilizing an automated brachial blood pressure cuff.</p> <p>Data shared/integrated: All pertinent patient activity (e.g. session completion, contraindications to exercise notifications, graduation, or discontinuation from the program), was documented by the EIMG® Pros</p>	<p>programmes as a population health management strategy. The implementation of EIMG® into Prisma Health clinics included: 1) programming the Physical Activity Vital Sign 2-question prompt, EIMG® best practice alerts, risk assessment, and order sets into the electronic health record (EHR), and 2) training providers and staff on the Clinical Workflow. The EIMG® Clinical Workflow programmed and incorporated into the EHR includes three standard modules: 1) PA assessment, 2) PA prescription, and 3) patient referral to a participating community PA center through a referral team.</p> <p>PA Assessment The nurse who rooms the patient captures the patient's current PA behaviour via a 2-question EHR prompt ("how many minutes per day do you exercise?" and "how many days/weeks?").</p> <p>PA Prescription The HCP informs eligible patients about the EIMG® program, reviews risks, and provides basic PA and health education through the EIM® Rx for Health handouts for exercising with chronic disease, developed by ACSM experts.</p> <p>Patient referral The HCP sends an electronic referral to the EIMG® Referral Team.</p> <p>EIMG referral team The "EIMG® Referral Team" (i.e. EIMG® Referral Coordinator and EIMG® Registered Nurse Care Coordinator) receives the referral (electronically sent through the EHR) from the participating health clinic. Then team then reviews the referred patient's EHR, contacts them, confirms eligibility and interest, and identifies the patient's preferred location. Since EIMG® guarantees an "open door policy" through the YMCA scholarship, the team also then determines the economic stability of the patient and whether the patient needs financial assistance. If the latter, the EIMG® Referral Coordinator connects the patient with YMCA financial assistant personnel to receive a scholarship, as the mission of the partnering YMCA is "no one is turned away for their inability to pay." Next, the EIMG® Referral Team electronically sends all HIPAA-compliant</p>	<p>Biometric measurements 2018-2019 - Adding EIMG® program participation to usual care (N = 159; n =100 patients with hypertension n = 59 non-hypertension) was associated with a significant decrease in body weight (pre 100.2kg vs post 98.2kg; p<0.001), with no significant decrease in resting heart rate (pre 76bpm vs post 75bpm; p=0.909), systolic blood pressure (pre 128mmHg vs post 126mmHg; p=0.069), or diastolic blood pressure (pre 81mmHg vs post 80mmHg; p=0.160).</p> <p>Sub-analysis: Patients with hypertension Adding EIMG® program participation to usual care for patients with hypertension at time of referral (n = 100) was associated with a statistically significant loss in body weight (pre 103.1kg vs post 101.3kg; p<0.001) and reduced systolic (pre 136mmHg vs post 129mmHg; p<0.001) and diastolic blood pressure (pre 86mmHg vs post 82mmHg; p<0.001), with no statistically significant change in resting heart rate (pre 77bpm vs post 76bpm; p=0.5).</p> <p>Revenue vs. Scholarship Reporting Scholarship provided to and revenue generated from EIMG® from 2016 to 2019 demonstrate that as the program grew, the percentage of patients who received scholarship as well as patients who paid also increased. Total amount of scholarship provided increased every year (Aug-Dec 2016= \$1,537; Jan-Dec 2017= \$3,686; Jan-Dec 2018= \$7,983; Jan-Dec 2019= \$10,240). Total Amount of Non-Scholarship Revenue also increased every year (Aug-Dec 2016= \$796; Jan-Dec 2017= \$1,791; Jan-Dec 2018= \$5,771; Jan-Dec 2019= \$21,648).</p>	

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	<p>and sent through secure fax to the EIMG® Referral Team. The EIMG® Referral Team then provides the patient's summary to the Healthcare providers (HCP) through the EHR.</p> <p>Outcomes: Referrals, enrollment and completion of programme; patient satisfaction; annual scholarship and revenue; body weight, blood pressure, and resting heart rate.</p> <p>Quality rating: Low quality</p>	<p>patient information to the corresponding EIMG® Site Coordinator at the selected community PA center.</p> <p>EIMG® Community PA Center Site Coordinators Upon receiving a patient referral, the EIMG® Site Coordinator contacts the patient, reviews logistic needs, and schedules the patient for onboarding with an EIMG® Professional (Pro). The (EIMG® Pros) are employees of the community PA centers,</p> <p>PA training programme The EIMG® exercise training program provides a small group-level (≤ 7 patients/ group), 12-week (60-minute sessions, 2 sessions/week), exercise protocol conducted by certified EIMG® Pros. The training sessions are guided by the social-cognitive theory following the principles that training is progressive, includes full body movements, and provides active education incorporated into training. Each exercise training session includes a cardiometabolic (aerobic training) component and a full-body musculoskeletal (resistance training) component. While extremely deconditioned patients start the exercise training program with as little as 5 min of aerobic exercise/session, the goal is for patients to progress through the 12 weeks to > 50 min/session of moderate-to-vigorous intensity exercise by graduation. EIMG® Pros are permitted to deliver the exercise sessions (using essential and recommended "building blocks," to patients based on their individual strengths, their unique class population, and opportunities/limitations within their specific facility setting (i.e., equipment, space, and scheduling). Additionally, to enhance behaviour change, patients are provided EIMG® Patient Education Handouts that teach them about adopting a healthy lifestyle (i.e., PA, diet and nutrition, stress management, goal setting, and social support).</p> <p>Healthcare delivery or treatment used: Physical activity training program</p>	<p>Additional findings:</p> <p>Exit survey 170 EIMG® graduates have completed the survey since its addition in March 2017. All components of the program and personnel (providers, project coordinator, and EIMG® Pros) received high satisfaction scores (Likert scale 1–5, with 5 rating "highly satisfied". All HCP scores were above 4.75. EIMG® Program Coordinator and EIMG® Pro satisfaction scores were above 4.9.</p>	

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/notes
		<p>Comparator: Before and after</p>		
<p>Scher, et al., (2022). <u>A community partnership to evaluate the feasibility of addressing food insecurity among adult patients in an urban healthcare system. Pilot and feasibility studies</u>, 8(1), 59.</p> <p>(USA)</p>	<p>Study design: Pilot non-randomised controlled study</p> <p>Aim: To assess the feasibility of a partnership between Henry Ford Health System (HFHS) and Gleaners Community Foodbank of Southeastern Michigan to implement and evaluate a food supplementation intervention initiated in a hospital outpatient clinic setting.</p> <p>Collaboration: A partnership between Henry Ford Health System (HFHS) and Gleaners Community Foodbank of Southeastern Michigan. The Hunger Vital Signs was used to screen HFHS internal medicine patients for food insecurity and data sharing infrastructure and agreements were established that were necessary for an HFHS-Gleaners partnership that would allow home delivery of food to consenting patients.</p> <p>Dates of data collection: Nov 2017 to May 2018</p> <p>Data collection methods: Emergency department visits and hospitalisations occurring during the post-index 12-month follow-up period were retrieved using the EMR for both groups. A patient satisfaction survey was used to assess satisfaction with the service. Patient-</p>	<p>Sample size: Intervention group (n=256), Control group (n=256) Patient satisfaction survey (n=260)</p> <p>Target population: Adults (18+) residing in metropolitan Detroit, who were considered to be 'food insecure' recruited from selected HFHS general internal medicine clinics.</p> <p>Health Condition(s): None specified for inclusion but patients had Asthma, Hypertension, Diabetes, CAD, CHF, COPD, CKD.</p> <p>Setting: Clinic to community</p> <p>Intervention details (Population Health Management approach utilised): The Henry's Groceries for Health program was designed by the HFHS Population Health Management Department in collaboration with Gleaners and the HFHS Department of Public Health Sciences. Patients presenting to participating clinics were initially screened for food insecurity by clinic medical assistants who then referred the patient to an ambulatory case manager who would complete the final portion of qualifying and enrolment. Upon meeting eligibility criteria and providing consent, were enrolled in the foodbank program. Enrolled patients received food supplementation twice per month for a total of 12 months, usually by home delivery, although some patients of the HFHS System Taylor Clinic travelled to the Gleaner's Food Bank located approximately 3 miles away from the clinic. The program began with a starter package containing staples such as spices, grains, low-sodium canned goods, and cooking oils. Subsequent food packages, in alignment with the USDA My Plate recommendations, contained 45% fruits and vegetables and 15% protein, 15%</p>	<p>Primary findings: A total of 6,519 deliveries were scheduled of which 5860 (89.9%) were "successful" (i.e., the enrolled participant received the food).</p> <p>ED Visits: At the 12-month post-index visit, n=123 patients in the intervention group made 279 ED visits, representing a -41.5% relative reduction from baseline and per person average reduction was 0.77 (95% CI 0.40 to 1.15). The historical comparison group also showed significant relative reductions in ED visits (-25.3%) and per person reduction 0.34 (95% CI 0.09 to 0.59) and while smaller in magnitude compared to the intervention group, the reduction was also significant. Difference-in-differences regression analysis was used to determine if the trend in ED visits over time was the same for the intervention group compared to that of the historical comparison group. The trend in ED visits for 12 months for the intervention group was 0.44 (95% CI -0.01 to 0.88) visits/patient lower than that of the historical comparison group.</p> <p>Hospitalisation: A relative reduction of -55.9% and a significant per person reduction of 0.15 (95% CI 0.01 to 0.29) in hospitalization were observed for the intervention group, compared to a -17.6% relative reduction and -0.004 (95% CI -0.06 to 0.07) per person reduction in hospitalizations for the historical comparison group that did not reach statistical significance. Difference-in-differences regression analysis showed the trend for hospitalizations for the intervention group was 0.15 (95%</p>	<p>The findings from this USA based study may not be directly applicable to the UK context. because the study was conducted in the USA as the study context may differ from Wales in terms of healthcare systems, and population characteristics.</p> <p>There were inconsistencies in the findings (the trend in both ED visits and hospitalization) between the text and the figures reducing the confidence in the findings</p>

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/ notes
	<p>reported data for this study was collected and managed using REDCap, a HIPAA-compliant electronic data capture tool for collecting and managing study data.</p> <p>Data shared/integrated: In addition to baseline and patient experience surveys, REDCap was used by both HFHS employees and Gleaners employees to securely communicate food delivery schedules. Gleaners employees had restricted access to REDCap reports and data collection features used to set up delivery schedules, make deliveries, and record outcomes for these activities. Participant information shared with Gleaners included consenting participant name, address, and phone number, in addition to food box preferences and delivery specifics.</p> <p>Outcomes: Food deliveries; emergency department visits; hospitalisations and patient satisfaction.</p> <p>Quality rating: Low quality</p>	<p>grains, and 25% dairy. Recipes, cooking tips, and food storage information were included with each food package. Participants received reminder calls for delivery the day before each scheduled delivery or pickup date from an HFHS Population Health staff member, who also assessed the need for changes to package contents. Based on this information, future packages were adjusted or customised.</p> <p>Healthcare delivery or treatment used: Food supplementation services</p> <p>Comparator: The historical comparison group was created using the HFHS electronic medical record (EMR). Initially, authors identified all patients with at least 1 encounter occurring between 11/1/2015 and 10/31/2016 and who were 18 years of age or older at the time of the encounter. The first encounter identified within this time frame for each patient served as the index visit.</p>	<p>CI-0.001 to 0.31) visits/patient lower than that of the historical comparison group.</p> <p>Additional findings: Patient Satisfaction Survey: 95.8% reported the food met their needs, 90.7% of participants reported eating all the food, 50.3% reported using the dietary tips and recipes included with the food boxes, and 36.5% reported sharing the meals with others.</p>	
<p>Stokes et al., (2021). Does prevention-focused integration lead to the triple aim? An evaluation of two new care models in England. Journal of</p>	<p>Study design: Non-randomised controlled study</p> <p>Aim: To examine the effectiveness of two integrated care models ('vanguards') in Salford and South Somerset in England, United Kingdom, in relation to patient experience, health outcomes and costs of care (the 'triple aim').</p>	<p>Sample size: Total 365,000 patients registered in 64 GP practices in Salford and South Somerset. Salford: 250,000 people registered in 45 GP practices: South Somerset: 115,000 people registered in 19 GP practices.</p> <p>Target population: some case management of high-risk patients, described as those over 65 years old in Salford, and those with multimorbidity in South Somerset.</p>	<p>Primary findings: Emergency admissions There was a small, but statistically significant increase in ambulatory care sensitive condition (ACSC) emergency admissions in the South Somerset site. The intervention effect was 0.005 (95% CI:0.002 to 0.007; p<0.001) when compared to the rest of England controls and 0.004 (95% CI:0.002 to 0.007; p<0.05) when compared to Rightcare controls, at an</p>	<p>Authors sought to evaluate the impact of the entire place based model of care (the 'intervention') on population level outcomes.</p>

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/ notes
<p><i>Health Services Research & Policy</i>, 26(2), 125-132.</p> <p>(UK)</p>	<p>Collaboration: The two study sites were part of the wider New Models of Care (Vanguard) programme that was launched in England in 2014 as a means to overcome the traditional boundaries between primary and secondary care and community services to support improvement and integration of services. Integrated care and cross-sector collaboration. Including but not limited to: integrated contact centre for patient navigation: central 'single-point-of-contact' phone hub for patients to contact; multidisciplinary group case management; and supporting 'community assets': investment in local neighbourhood groups and activities, such as sports groups, to encourage community engagement in healthy social behaviours.</p> <p>Dates of data collection: April 2009- April 2018</p> <p>Data collection methods: Authors used two nationally representative sources of data. For measuring patient experience and health status, authors used the national General Practitioner Patient Survey (GPPS), a postal survey administered to a sample of registered patients from all GP practices in England annually, which has been conducted twice a year from 2012</p>	<p>Health condition(s): chronic conditions and high-risk patients.</p> <p>Setting: two integrated care sites, Salford and South Somerset, England, UK.</p> <p>Intervention details (Population Health Management approach utilised): Salford and South Somerset are 2 of 9 of the wider New Models of Care (Vanguard) programme sites that implemented 'integrated primary and acute care systems' (PACS). Two integrated care models in Salford and South Somerset, UK, using the 'the entire place-based model of care'.</p> <p>The two study sites were part of the wider New Models of Care (Vanguard) programme that was launched in England in 2014 as a means to overcome the traditional boundaries between primary and secondary care and community services to support improvement and integration of services. Participating sites received government funding and support to pilot population health management approaches from 2015 (until March 2018). Salford and South Somerset were among the nine sites that implemented 'integrated primary and acute care systems' (PACS), both seeking to achieve the triple aim.</p> <p>Healthcare delivery or treatment used: It was looking at improving health outcomes.</p> <p>Comparator: Usual care in other England sites commonly targeting high-risk patients using case management approaches (Rest of England controls and NHS Rightcare controls).</p>	<p>additional 5 admissions per 1000 registered patients per year. No significant differences were reported for the Salford site.</p> <p>Sub-analysis: Patients with multimorbidity No significant differences were reported for the Salford site. However a significant increase in ACSC emergency admissions was found for the those with multimorbidity at the South Somerset site when compared to the rest of England controls (Intervention effect: 0.008; 95% CI: 0.032 to 0.012; p<0.001) and when compared to Rightcare controls (Intervention effect: 0.006; 95% CI: 0.0004 to 0.012; p<0.05).</p> <p>Primary care utilisation No effects on primary care utilisation (participants reporting seeing a GP or nurse within the previous 6 months) were reported in either intervention site In Salford, the intervention effect was -0.005 (95% CI:-0.018 to 0.008) when compared to the rest of England controls and -0.002 (95% CI:-0.017 to 0.013) when compared to Rightcare controls. In South Somerset the intervention effect was 0.001 (95% CI:-0.009 to 0.011) when compared to the rest of England controls and 0.003 (95% CI:-0.010 to 0.016) when compared to Rightcare controls. Findings identified an initial increase in primary care utilisation in the first six months in South Somerset. Similar trends were observed for Salford, but these were not statistically different from control sites, and neither were sustained over time.</p> <p>Sub-analysis: Patients with multimorbidity No effects on primary care utilisation were found for either site. In Salford, the intervention effect was 0.003 (95% CI:-0.013 to 0.19) when compared to the rest of England controls and</p>	

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/ notes
	<p>until 2016 (annually from 2017). To assess health care costs, the Hospital Episode Statistics (HES) database for England (from April 2009 to March 2018). This database includes administrative data recording all patient contacts with National Health Service (NHS) hospitals.</p> <p>Data shared: In Salford: integrated contact centre for patient navigation: central 'single-point-of-contact' phone hub for patients to contact, including a health coaching component for selected individuals. Some joining of health and social care records through the Salford Integrated Record. Additionally, 'Salford Together' is a partnership between Salford City Council, NHS Salford Clinical Commissioning Group, Salford Royal NHS Foundation Trust (leading role), Salford Primary Care Together and Greater Manchester Mental Health NHS Foundation Trust. In South Somerset: Leadership by Symphony Programme Board, co-located in Yeovil hospital. The Symphony Programme is a collaboration between Yeovil District Hospital NHS Foundation Trust, south Somerset Healthcare GP Federation, Somerset CCG, Somerset Partnership, the voluntary sector in South Somerset (SSVCA) and Somerset County Council. Plans to join up electronic records, but difficulties in implementing.</p>		<p>0.005 (95% CI:-0.013 to 0.024) when compared to Rightcare controls. In South Somerset the intervention effect was -0.001 (95% CI:-0.012 to 0.010) when compared to the rest of England controls and 0.002 (95% CI:-0.012 to 0.016) when compared to Rightcare controls.</p> <p>Total cost of secondary care per registered patient and year SA statistically significant increase in the costs of secondary care over the post-intervention period were reported in both intervention sites, at £73.81 per registered patient per year in Salford and £44.55 in South Somerset. In Salford the intervention effect was 73.866 (95% CI:37.641 to 109.971; p<0.001) when compared to the rest of England controls and 136.574 (95% CI:62.098 to 211.050; p<0.001) when compared to the Rightcare controls. In South Somerset the intervention effect was 44.545 (95% CI:20.351 to 68.739; p<0.001) when compared to the rest of England controls and 83.773 (95% CI:40.966 to 126.579; p<0.001) when compared to the Rightcare controls.</p> <p>Sub-analysis: Patients with multimorbidity South Somerset had consistently higher total costs of secondary care for multi-morbid patients (their primary target group), whereas Salford did not. In Salford the intervention effect was 26.674 (95% CI:-31.596 to 84.943) when compared to the rest of England controls and 101.026 (95% CI:-4.099 to 206.151) when compare to Rightcare controls. Whereas in South Somerset the intervention effect was 80.791 (95% CI:44.842 to 116.740; p<0.001) when compared to the rest of England controls and 103.619 (95% CI:57.543 to 149.696; p<0.001) when compare to Rightcare controls.</p>	

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/ notes
	<p>Outcomes: For the primary analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) patient experience (2) generic health status (health-related quality of life) as measured by the EQ-5D 5 L index. (3) health care costs. <p>Secondary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (4) cost per user of secondary care, (5) ambulatory care sensitive condition (ACSC) emergency admissions and (6) primary care utilisation. <p>Quality rating: Low quality</p>		<p>Cost per user of secondary care</p> <p>A statistically significant increase in the total cost of secondary care per user was reported at both intervention sites. In Salford, the total cost of secondary care increased by approximately £138 per person per year, the intervention effect was 138.472 (95% CI:76.378 to 200.566; p<0.001) when compared to rest of England controls and 156.609 (95% CI:57.470 to 255.748; p<0.05) when compared to Right-care controls. In South Somerset, the total cost of secondary care per user increased by approximately £130 per person per year, the intervention effect was 129.717 (95% CI:68.256 to 191.178; p<0.001) when compared to rest of England controls and 168.385 (95% CI:93.876 to 242.893; p<0.001) when compared to Right-care controls.</p> <p>Sub-analysis: Patients with multimorbidity</p> <p>The increases in cost per user for those with multimorbidity were higher compared to the whole population. In Salford the total cost of secondary care per user increased by approximately £173 per person per year, the intervention effect was 173.356 (95% CI:53.651 to 293.062; p<0.05) when compared to rest of England controls and 209.216 (95% CI:22.293 to 396.138; p<0.05) when compared to Right-care controls. In South Somerset the total cost of secondary care per user increased by approximately £268 per person per year, the intervention effect was 267.689 (95% CI:150.843 to 384.535; p<0.001) when compared to rest of England controls and 328.628 (95% CI:184.760 to 472.495; p<0.001) when compared to Rightcare controls.</p>	

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/ notes
			<p>Additional findings: There were no statistically significant differences in intervention sites compared to controls in terms of patient experience or health status as measured by EQ5D. There was a statistically significant increase in patient experience of care in South Somerset at the end of year one and an initial increase in primary care utilisation in the first six months. Similar trends were observed for Salford, but these were not statistically different from control sites.</p>	
<p>Sioni, et al., (2025). Short-term gains, enduring potential: an integrated SDOH-focused care model delivers cost savings and patient-reported benefits. Population Health Management, 28(3), 161-172.</p> <p>(US)</p>	<p>Study design: Matched cohort study</p> <p>Aim: to assess whether a proactive, SDoH-oriented care management model could reduce utilisation, lower costs, and improve patient-reported outcomes (PROs) among high-need, high-cost (HNHC) adults.</p> <p>Collaboration: Care managers consulted with internal providers and external community-based organizations (e.g., social workers or pharmacists) to address culturally tailored or complex needs.</p> <p>Dates of data collection: Not stated</p> <p>Data collection methods: Data was collected from multiple sources: Electronic Health Records (EHRs)—capturing demographic variables, clinical details, monthly SDoH checks, and baseline Health-related quality of life measures. Administrative Claims—providing ED visits,</p>	<p>Sample size: 526 participants (n=263 intervention group, n=263 comparison group)</p> <p>Target population: High-need high-cost patients with 2 or more hospital admissions or 4 or more ED visits in a prior 6-month.</p> <p>Health condition: None specified for inclusion but patients considered High-need high-cost.</p> <p>Setting: Four urban primary care clinics</p> <p>Intervention details (Population Health Management approach utilised): A care management model: 1. Monthly SDoH Reassessments—via phone or in-person to detect evolving social barriers (e.g., housing or food insecurity). 2. Real-Time ADT Alerts—through a health information exchange (HIE) platform, triggering outreach within 24 hours of admission or discharge. 3. Medication Management—relying on evidence-based guidance on pharmacy logs, refills, and adherence. 4. Appointment Coordination—scheduling follow-up visits, confirming attendance, and gathering external provider records.</p>	<p>Key findings:</p> <p>Emergency department utilisation Temporal trends in ED usage reveal a more pronounced decline for the intervention cohort compared to the comparison group over 60 days. ED visits dropped by 0.13 at 30 days (P < 0.001) and 0.17 at 60 days (P < 0.001) in the intervention arm, whereas the comparison arm experienced smaller or nonsignificant reductions. These data suggest that monthly SDOH checks, real-time ADT alerts, and medication oversight jointly curtailed avoidable acute care encounters.</p> <p>Hospital admissions Hospital admission rates also decreased more substantially in the intervention group, with between-group differences of 0.08 at 30 days and 0.12 at 60 days (P < 0.001 for both).</p> <p>Costs The intervention cohort's per participant costs fell from \$6,019 pre-enrolment to \$2,422 post-enrolment, a net decrease of \$3,222 (P<0.001) this highlights the estimated 6.9:1 return on investment (ROI), underscoring the near-term economic viability of integrating SDOH outreach with medication oversight.³³ Sensitivity</p>	

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/ notes
	<p>hospital admissions, and pharmacy records.</p> <p>Health Information Exchange (HIE) Platform—generating real-time admission discharge transfer (ADT) alerts, enabling prompt post-discharge outreach. Pharmacy Logs—verifying prescription pickups and flagging missed refills or potential non-adherence. This integrated dataset supported tracking of utilisation changes and patient-level measures</p> <p>Data shared: By integrating pharmacy data (e.g., refill records), real-time ADT alerts, and monthly SDoH assessments, care managers can address emergent issues before they escalate.</p> <p>Outcomes: Emergency department utilisation, hospital admissions, costs, health-related quality of life, patient satisfaction</p> <p>Quality rating: Low quality</p>	<p>Healthcare delivery or treatment used: Care management model - integrating monthly SDoH screenings, medication oversight, and real-time admission discharge transfer alerts.</p> <p>Comparator: Usual care, involving standard office visits and ad hoc clinician-led interventions without systematic monthly SDOH checks.</p>	<p>analyses adjusting ED and admission costs – 10% did not meaningfully alter these financial conclusions, indicating that the results are robust to modest cost variation.</p> <p>Health-related quality of life EQ-5D-5L (Health-related quality of life). Across the entire sample (n = 526), EQ-5D-5L scores increased from a pre-intervention mean of 0.700 (SD = 0.15) to 0.765 (SD = 0.14), indicating an overall gain of +0.065 (t(525) = 12.95, P<0.001). This change corresponded to a Cohen’s d of 0.85, signifying a large effect size in favour of the intervention. In group-specific analyses, the enrolled (intervention) group improved from 0.720 to 0.802 (t(525) = -14.88, P < 0.001), whereas the comparison group’s increase (0.604 to 0.612) was nonsignificant (t(262) = -1.88, P = 0.069). Subgroup analyses revealed that middle-aged adults (36–50) with private insurance achieved the largest EQ-5D-5L gain of +0.137 (95% CI [0.115, 0.159]).³⁴ These findings suggest that combining monthly SDoH assessments, medication checks, and real-time ADT alerts can drive clinically meaningful short-term improvements in health-related quality of life.</p> <p>Patient satisfaction Net Promoter Score (NPS) (patient satisfaction). For NPS, participants overall exhibited a mean increase from 17.78 (SD = 7.6) to 22.19 (SD = 8.5), a difference of +4.41 [t(525) = 16.75, P < 0.001], equivalent to Cohen’s d = 1.05, denoting a large effect size. Group-specific data indicated that the enrolled arm improved from 19.49 to 28.22 [t(525) = -43.12, P < 0.001], while the comparison group’s change (16.26 to 15.55) was not statistically significant</p>	

Citation (Country) url/doi	Study Details	Participants, setting and intervention	Key findings	Observations/notes
			<p>[t(262) = 1.71, P =0.091]. Subgroup analyses identified younger adults (18–35) with private insurance as having the most substantial NPS gain of +9.56 points. These robust effect sizes underscore that participants experienced not only lower acute utilisation but also higher satisfaction—a critical dimension under value-based care contracts that emphasise patient experience.</p> <p>Additional findings: Subgroup analyses and equity considerations. Analyses by race/ethnicity and insurance status revealed slight variations in effect sizes. Medicare/Medicaid beneficiaries exhibited marginally larger declines in ED use than those with commercial/private insurance (P = 0.026). Although most subgroups benefited, some non-White cohorts exhibited smaller EQ-5D-5L gains, suggesting potential areas for culturally or linguistically tailored interventions. These patterns underscore the importance of ongoing refinements to address disparate outcomes across demographic strata.</p>	

7.3 Quality appraisal

Table 5. Quality appraisal results for quasi-experimental studies

		Domain	INTERNAL VALIDITY Bias related to:								Statistical conclusion validity	Methodological quality
			Temporal precedence	Selection and allocation	Confounding factors	Administration of intervention/exposure	Assessment, detection and measurement of the outcome			Participant retention		
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8		
Study	Outcome	Result										
Ajibola et al., (2025)	Patients screened	Post intervention	Y	N	U	U	N	Y	Y	U	U	Low
	Findhelp.org users	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	U	U	
	Patients connected to a Findhelp.org programme	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	U	U	
Murphy et al., (2018)	Costs	Post intervention	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	U	U	Low
	ED Visits	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	U	U	
	Admissions	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	U	U	
	Readmissions	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	U	U	
Porter et al., (2022)	Patient survey	Post intervention	Y	N	U	U	N	Y	Y	N	U	Low
	Costs	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
	Body Weight	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
	Resting heart rate	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
	Systolic bp	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
	Diastolic bp	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	

Scher et al., (2022)	ED visits	Post intervention	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	U	Low
	Hospitalisation	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
	Patient satisfaction	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
Stokes et al., (2021)	Patient experience	Post intervention	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	U	Low
	Health status (EQ5D)	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
	Total cost of secondary care per patient and year	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
	Cost per user of secondary care	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
	ACSC emergency admissions	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
	Primary care utilisation	Post intervention					N	Y	Y	N	U	
Key: Y=Yes, N=No, U=Unclear, N/A=Not applicable												

1. Is it clear in the study what is the “cause” and what is the “effect”?
2. Was there a control group?
3. Were participants included in any comparisons similar?
4. Were the participants included in any comparisons receiving similar treatment/care, other than the exposure or intervention of interest?
5. Were there multiple measurements of the outcome, both pre and post the intervention/exposure?
6. Were the outcomes of participants included in any comparisons measured in the same way?
7. Were outcomes measured in a reliable way?
8. Was follow-up complete and if not, were differences between groups in terms of their follow-up adequately described and analysed?
9. Was appropriate statistical analysis used?

Table 6. Quality appraisal results for randomised controlled trials

		Domain	INTERNAL VALIDITY Bias related to:										Statistical conclusion validity			Methodological quality
			Selection and allocation			Administration of intervention/exposure			Assessment, detection and measurement of the outcome			Participant retention				
			Question no	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Study	Outcome	Result														
Hitsman et al., (2022)	Quitline engagement at 6 weeks	Post intervention	U	U	U	U	U	Y	U	Y	Y	U	N	U	U	
	Quitline treatment utilisation at 14 weeks	Post intervention							U	Y	Y	U	N	U		
	Smoking cessation at 28 weeks	Post intervention							U	Y	Y	U	N	U		
Key: Y=Yes, N=No, U=Unclear, N/A=Not applicable																

1. Was true randomisation used for assignment of participants to treatment groups?
2. Was allocation to treatment groups concealed?
3. Were treatment groups similar at baseline?
4. Were participants blind to treatment assignment?
5. Were those delivering the treatment blind to treatment assignment?
6. Were treatment groups treated identically other than the intervention of interest?
7. Were outcome assessors blind to treatment assignment?
8. Were outcomes measured in the same way for treatment groups?
9. Were outcomes measured in a reliable way?
10. Was follow up complete and if not, were differences between groups in terms of their follow up adequately described and analysed?
11. Were participants analysed in the groups to which they were randomised?
12. Was appropriate statistical analysis used?
13. Was the trial design appropriate and deviations from the standard RCT design accounted for in the conduct and analysis of the trial?

Table 7. Quality appraisal results for Cohort studies

Question no/ Study	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Methodological quality
Sioni et al., (2025)	Y	Y	Y	N	N/A	N/A	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	Low
Key: Y=Yes, N=No, U=Unclear, N/A=Not applicable												

1. Were the two groups similar and recruited from the same population?
2. Were the exposures measured similarly to assign people to both exposed and unexposed groups?
3. Was the exposure measured in a valid and reliable way?
4. Were confounding factors identified?
5. Were strategies to deal with confounding factors stated?
6. Were the groups/participants free of the outcome at the start of the study (or at the moment of exposure)?
7. Were the outcomes measured in a valid and reliable way?
8. Was the follow up time reported and sufficient to be long enough for outcomes to occur?
9. Was follow up complete, and if not, were the reasons to loss to follow up described and explored?
10. Were strategies to address incomplete follow up utilized?
11. Was appropriate statistical analysis used

7.4 Components of PHM

PHM as an overall approach has been described and defined in the literature many times. However, as previously described, PHM approaches can vary significantly, and the specific components or elements which need to be incorporated to constitute a PHM intervention is less well defined. A scoping review described the complexity of implementing PHM strategies and provided six components (Van Ede et al., 2023) that we felt incorporated the main key components of PHM. These included: an accountable regional organisation; a cross-domain business model; an integrated data infrastructure; a co-designing workforce and community; population data analytics and emergent implementation strategies (Van Ede et al., 2023). While it is not expected that every PHM approach or intervention would incorporate all six components, for the purposes of this review, we have used the components to help us understand and define what an ideal PHM approach would involve.

All included studies incorporated some of the key PHM components and elements as described by Van Ede et al., (2023), see Table 8. However, the information related to the design or creation of the interventions (incorporating PHM approaches) within included studies was often poorly reported or lacking detail, leading to uncertainty around whether these components had been included. Therefore, the information provided in Table 8 may not accurately reflect which components/elements were actually incorporated when the PHM approaches were designed, but rather simply reflects the information provided in the individual studies. While it is understood that an intervention (incorporating PHM approaches) is unlikely to incorporate every component seen in Table 8, it is important that studies assessing interventions (incorporating PHM approaches) be transparent in their approaches.

Table 8. Key components and elements of PHM (adapted from Van Ede, A et al., 2023) identified in the included studies

Key components	Elements	References						
		Ajibola et al (2025)	Hitsman et al (2022)	Murphy et al (2018)	Porter et al (2020)	Scher et al (2022)	Stokes et al (2021)	Sioni et al (2025)
Accountable regional organisation	Group of stakeholders with financial arrangements	U	U	Y	Y	U	Y	Y
	Co-ordination and support structures	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Multi-stakeholder governance structure across continuum of care	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	prevention of new fragmentation	Y	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	Y
	Strategy building supported by organisational	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Cross domain business model	Additional funding	U	U	Y	U	U	Y	Y
	Financial incentives aligned with system goals	U	U	U	U	U	U	U
	Scale	U	U	U	Y	U	U	U
	Goals and objectives supported by resources	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Workforce	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Integrated data infrastructure	Investment and business plan to realise data-infrastructure	U	U	U	U	U	U	U
	Workforce	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y
	IT infrastructure	Y	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Follow patient with data across the continuum of care	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Co-designing workforce and community	Community engagement	U	Y	Y	U	U	U	Y
	Workforce	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Understanding patient and population	Y	Y	Y	U	Y	U	Y
Population data analytics	Data availability	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Evidence based evaluation	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Agreements on data collection	U	Y	U	Y	Y	U	Y
Emergent implementation strategies	Stakeholder engagement	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Supportive structures	Y	U	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	Strategy	Y	U	Y	Y	U	U	Y
	Maintain momentum	Y	U	U	U	U	Y	Y
	Flexibility based on learning cycle	Y	U	Y	Y	U	Y	U

Y=Yes; N=No; U=Unclear.

7.5 PROGRESS-PLUS mapping

Four studies provided some form of sub-group analysis to further explore the impact of the intervention on the PROGRESS-PLUS components. They explored the impact on populations with differing characteristics (Murphy et al., 2018; Porter et al., 2020; Stokes et al., 2021; Sioni et al., 2025). This included findings specifically for those with a mental or behavioural health condition compared to controls (Murphy et al., 2018), those with hypertension before and after the intervention (Porter et al., 2020), or findings specifically for those with multimorbidity compared to usual care controls (Stokes et al., 2021). Sioni et al., (2025) reported some sub-group analysis based on race/ethnicity.

Some included studies lacked a control group, or had control groups with similar characteristics, the findings do not necessarily show the impact of the interventions on health inequalities. In order to evaluate the impact of an intervention on specific health inequalities a sub-group analysis according to some of the variables included in PROGRESS-PLUS is required (Oliver et al., 2008). Although all studies included disadvantaged or at-risk populations, they did not consider how socioeconomic factors, ethnicity, or social capital affect access and success of interventions.

Table 9. PROGRESS-PLUS mapping

Reference							
	Ajibola et al (2025)	Hitsman et al (2022)	Murphy et al (2018)	Porter et al (2020)	Scher et al (2022)	Stokes et al (2021)	Sioni et al (2025)
Intervention Aim (in terms of population)							
General population							
Disadvantaged or at-risk	Food insecurity, financial constraints and transportation access	Low-income smokers	One or more chronic conditions	Physically inactive and/or a chronic condition	Food insecurity	Older adults and those with multimorbidity	High-need High-risk
Reducing social gradients							
PROGRESS-Plus characteristics explored in the outcomes							
Place of residence							
Race/ethnicity/ Culture/ language							Race/ ethnicity
Occupation							
Gender/sex							
Religion							
Education							
Socioeconomic status							
Social capital							
Plus – age ¹							
Plus – disability/ condition ¹			Mental or behavioural health conditions	Hypertension		Multimorbidity	
Plus – features of relationships ²							

Plus – time-dependent relationships ³							
¹ refers to personal characteristics associated with discrimination ² refers to features of relationships that may include elements such as smoking parents, being excluded from school etc. ³ refers to time-dependent relationships such as leaving the hospital, respite care, or other instances where a person may be temporarily at a disadvantage							

7.6 Information available on request

The following are available on request: protocol; full search strategies.

8 ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

8.1 Conflicts of interest

The authors declare they have no conflicts of interest to report.

8.2 Acknowledgements

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9 APPENDIX

9.1 Appendix 1 Reference list of the 48 excluded studies

References	Country	Study design	Study Aim	Reasons for exclusion
Ashburner et al., (2017) Chronic Disease Outcomes From Primary Care Population Health Program Implementation <i>Am J Manag Care</i> , 23(12), 728-735.	USA	Quasi-experimental	Implementation of a chronic disease management health IT tool within primary care to improve performance quality measures.	Not PHM – disease management, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Baer et al., (2020a) Integrating an online weight management program with population health management in primary care: Design, methods, and baseline data from the PROPS randomized controlled trial (Partnerships for Reducing Overweight and Obesity with Patient-centered Strategies) . <i>Contemporary Clinical Trials</i> , 95, p.106026.	USA	Cluster-randomised controlled trial	To examine the effectiveness of an online weight management program integrated with population health management support.	Not PHM – weight management program, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Baer et al., (2020b). Effect of an online weight management program integrated with population health management on weight change: a randomized clinical trial . <i>Jama</i> , 324(17), pp.1737-1746	USA	Cluster-randomised controlled trial	To compare the effectiveness of a combined intervention, including an online weight management program plus population health management, with the online program only and with usual care.	Not PHM – weight management program, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Berkowitz et al., (2015). Building equity improvement into quality improvement: reducing socioeconomic disparities in colorectal cancer screening as part of population health management . <i>Journal of general internal</i>	USA	Interrupted time series (ITS)	To determine if implementation of a system-wide screening intervention was able to reduce disparities while increasing overall colorectal cancer screening rates.	Not PHM-Technology for Optimizing Population Care (TopCare) consisted of both a health IT platform and a population management workforce, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.

<i>medicine</i> , 30(7), pp.942-949				
Billups et al., (2025). Centralized outreach with embedded pharmacist e-consultation to reduce therapeutic inertia and improve blood pressure control . <i>American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy</i> , 82(22), pp.1249-1255	USA	Retrospective cohort	To evaluate the impact of a population health intervention to reduce therapeutic inertia and improve hypertension control in a multi-practice primary care setting.	Not PHM- Care quality improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Butler et al., (2010) Diabetes Mellitus Disease Management in a Safety Net Hospital System: Translating Evidence into Practice . <i>Population Health Management</i> , 13(6), pp.319-324.	USA	Quasi-experimental before and after	To translate the American Diabetes Association guidelines for diabetes mellitus care into clinical practice and increase number of patients achieving recommended adherence process measures and disease control	Not PHM – disease management, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Coffey et al., (2019) Implementing a systematic approach to deprescribing proton pump inhibitor therapy in older adults . <i>The Senior Care Pharmacist</i> , 34(1), pp.47-55.	USA	Prospective interventional pilot	To investigate the efficacy of an initiative aimed at reducing the unnecessary use of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) in elderly patients.	Not PHM – Quality improvement and medication review, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Deglow et al., (2024). Pharmacist-driven deprescribing to reduce anticholinergic burden in veterans with dementia . <i>Federal Practitioner</i> , 41(12), p.408.	USA	Before and after	To determine the impact of pharmacist-driven deprescribing on the anticholinergic burden in veterans with dementia.	Not PHM – Quality improvement and medication review, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Fakourfar and Rao (2023) Pharmacy student involvement in population health management of statin quality measures . <i>Journal of the American College of Clinical Pharmacy</i> , 6(5), pp.481-487	USA	Retrospective, before and after	Remodelled workflow to be more standardized and incorporate advanced pharmacy students into the statin quality measure improvement process.	Not PHM – service delivery/quality improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.

Gohard-erakhshan et al., (2021). Population management approach to kidney stone care improves patient compliance to preventive measures and reduces resource utilization in patients at high risk for stone recurrence. <i>Urology Practice</i> , 8(2), pp.253-258	USA	Retrospective	To evaluate a kidney stone population management program's role in patient compliance with American Urological Association metabolic studies and assess the impact on office encounters, operating room procedures and emergency department visits for known high risk kidney stone patients.	Not PHM – disease management/care improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Golas et al., (2021). Predictive analytics and tailored interventions improve clinical outcomes in older adults: a randomized controlled trial. <i>Npj Digital Medicine</i> , 4(1), p.97.	USA	RCT	To evaluate the impact of this Stepped-Care approach on the healthcare utilisation and healthcare costs of older patients using a Personal Emergency Response System.	Not PHM – Homecare management programme, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Grant et al., (2003). Impact of population management with direct physician feedback on care of patients with type 2 diabetes. <i>Diabetes Care</i> , 26(8), pp.2275-2280.	USA	Controlled study	To assess the impact of population management versus usual care on metabolic risk factor testing and management in patients with type 2 diabetes.	Not PHM – disease management, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Grossmeier et al., (2013). Impact of a comprehensive population health management program on health care costs. <i>Journal of occupational and environmental medicine</i> , 55(6), pp.634-643.	USA	Quasi-experimental	Assess the influence of participation in a population health management (PHM) program on health care costs.	Not PHM – disease management. No multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Harris et al., (2022). Impact of a comprehensive population health management program on health care costs. <i>Journal of occupational and environmental</i>	USA	Interrupted time series	To improve PPSV23 vaccination rates for children at high risk for IPD who were seen in 3 specialty clinics from 20% to 50% over a 12-month period.	Not PHM – integrated care/quality improvement.

<i>medicine</i> , 55(6), pp.634-643.				
James et al., (2018). Impact of a population health management intervention on disparities in cardiovascular disease control . <i>Journal of general internal medicine</i> , 33(4), pp.463-470.	USA	Retrospective, before and after	To determine whether a program that used PHCs decreased racial/ethnic disparities in LDL cholesterol and blood pressure control.	Not PHM – disease management, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Jhamb et al., (2024). Electronic health record population health management for chronic kidney disease care: a cluster randomized clinical trial . <i>JAMA internal medicine</i> , 184(7), pp.737-747.	USA	Pragmatic cluster randomised clinical trial	To compare the effectiveness of an electronic health record–based population health management intervention vs usual care for reducing chronic kidney disease (CKD) progression and improving evidence-based care in high-risk CKD.	Not PHM – disease management, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Kangovi et al., (2017). Community health worker support for disadvantaged patients with multiple chronic diseases: a randomized clinical trial . <i>American journal of public health</i> , 107(10), pp.1660-1667	USA	RCT	To determine whether a community health worker intervention improved outcomes in a low-income population with multiple chronic conditions.	Not PHM – disease management, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Kaphingst et al., (2024). Uptake of cancer genetic services for chatbot vs standard-of-care delivery models: the BRIDGE randomized clinical trial . <i>JAMA network open</i> , 7(9), p.e2432143.	USA	RCT	To examine whether chatbot and standard of care approaches are equivalent in completion of pretest cancer genetic services and genetic testing.	Not PHM – Quality improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Kozłowska et al., (2020). Population health management in diabetes care: combining clinical audit, risk	UK	Mixed methods evaluation	To evaluate the acceptability, feasibility and short-term impact on primary care of implementing a population approach intervention using direct	Not PHM – Integrated care, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.

stratification, and multidisciplinary virtual clinics in a community setting to improve diabetes care in a geographically defined population. An integrated diabetes care pilot in the North East locality, Oxfordshire, UK. <i>International journal of integrated care</i> , 20(4), p.21			observations of the clinics and surveys of participating clinicians.	
LaMantia et al., (2015). The aging brain care medical home: preliminary data . <i>Journal of the American Geriatrics Society</i> , 63(6), pp.1209-1213	USA	Before and after	To improve the care, health outcomes, and medical costs of Medicare beneficiaries with dementia or depression across central Indiana.	Not PHM – Integrated care/ Care improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets.
Levitz et al., (2022). Reducing cardiovascular risk for patients with diabetes: an evidence-based, population health management program . <i>The Journal for Healthcare Quality (JHQ)</i> , 44(2), pp.103-112.	USA	Mixed-methods evaluation	Evaluation of a program called Preventing Heart Attacks and Strokes Everyday (PHASE), which combined an evidence-based medication protocol with population health management and team-based care strategies.	Not PHM – Integrated care, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Lobach et al., (2008). Showing Health Information Value in a Community Network	USA	RCT	To evaluate the impact of using health information technology to facilitate appropriate care utilization, coordination and quality in a community setting using a population health management model.	Not PHM – Care improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Lobach et al., (2012). Improving Care Transitions for Complex Patients through Decision Support	USA	RCT	To develop and evaluate a decision support system that will increase the availability of clinical information at ambulatory care practices following three types of care transitions (hospital discharges, emergency department encounters and specialty care evaluations).	Not PHM – Care improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Loeppke et al., (2008). The impact	USA	Matched case control	To evaluate the impact of an integrated population	Not PHM – integrated population health

<p>of an integrated population health enhancement and disease management program on employee health risk, health conditions, and productivity. <i>Population health management</i>, 11(6), pp.287-296.</p>			<p>health enhancement program on employee health risks, health conditions, and productivity.</p>	<p>enhancement program for employees, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets</p>
<p>Martin et al., (2021). Implementation of a pharmacist-managed population health monitoring tool for disease modifying therapies in treatment of patients with multiple sclerosis in a veterans affairs medical center. <i>Journal of the American College of Clinical Pharmacy</i>, 5(1), pp.49-57</p>	USA	Before and after	<p>To (1) establish specific guidelines for disease modifying therapies monitoring that would be used to create a population health management (PHM) tool via electronic dashboard to allow targeted patient interventions by the neurology clinical pharmacy specialist, and (2) describe pharmacist interventions before and after dashboard implementation.</p>	<p>Not PHM – Quality improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets</p>
<p>Matthews et al., (2016). Comparison of 2 population health management approaches to increase vitamin B12 monitoring in patients taking metformin. <i>Annals of Pharmacotherapy</i>, 50(10), pp.840-846.</p>	USA	Group-randomised design	<p>To compare the effectiveness of and time required for 2 pharmacist-driven population health management interventions to improve vitamin B12 monitoring in patients taking metformin.</p>	<p>Not PHM – health care delivery, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets</p>
<p>Mattke et al., (2009). Impact of 2 employer-sponsored population health management programs on medical care cost and utilization. <i>The American Journal of Managed Care</i>, 15(2), pp.113-120.</p>	USA	Observational study	<p>To estimate the overall impact of a population health management program (Integrated health management programs combining disease prevention and disease management services for employers) and its components on cost and utilization.</p>	<p>Not PHM – disease management program, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets</p>
<p>Mehta et al., (2016). Race/ethnicity and adoption of a</p>	USA	Retrospective cohort study	<p>To examine the association between race/ethnicity and the receipt of</p>	<p>Not PHM – service improvement, no</p>

<p>population health management approach to colorectal cancer screening in a community-based healthcare system. <i>Journal of general internal medicine</i>, 31(11), pp.1323-1330</p>			<p>colorectal cancer screening and timely follow-up of positive results before and after implementation of a screening program.</p>	<p>multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets</p>
<p>Merchant et al., (2016). Effectiveness of population health management using the propeller health asthma platform: a randomized clinical trial. <i>The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology: In Practice</i>, 4(3), pp.455-463.</p>	USA	RCT	<p>To evaluate the effectiveness of the Propeller Health Platform for asthma management in a real-world outpatient clinic setting to assess the contribution to asthma control as measured by participants SABA use and the Asthma Control Test</p>	<p>Not PHM – disease management, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets</p>
<p>Murphy et al., (2018a) Key design considerations when calculating cost savings for population health management programs in an observational setting. <i>Health services research</i>, 53, pp.3107-3124</p>	USA	Quasi-experimental design	<p>To illustrate the impact of key quasi-experimental design elements on cost savings measurement for population health management programs.</p>	<p>Includes same data as Murphy et al (2018) study included in this rapid review</p>
<p>Murphy et al., (2013). A method for estimating cost savings for population health management programs. <i>Health services research</i>, 48(2pt1), pp.582-602.</p>	USA	Quasi-experimental design	<p>To develop a quasi-experimental method for estimating program savings that mitigates common sources of confounding, supports regular updates for continued program monitoring, and estimates model precision</p>	<p>Not PHM – Model development, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets</p>
<p>Nikolova-Simons et al., (2021). A randomized trial examining the effect of predictive analytics and tailored interventions on the cost of care. <i>NPJ Digital Medicine</i>, 4(1), p.92</p>	USA	Randomised controlled trial	<p>To evaluate the impact of a Stepped-Care intervention (predictive analytics combined with tailored interventions) on the healthcare costs of older adults using a Personal Emergency Response System</p>	<p>Not PHM – quality care/predictive model, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets</p>

Orzol et al., (2018). The impact of a health information technology–focused patient-centered medical neighborhood program among Medicare beneficiaries in primary care practices: the effect on patient outcomes and spending. <i>Medical Care</i> , 56(4), pp.299-307	USA	Matched case control	To estimate impacts of TransforMED’s HCIA-funded program on patient outcomes and Medicare parts A and B spending.	Not PHM – IT software, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Ostwald et al., (2023). The societal impact of Inclisiran in England: evidence from a population health approach. <i>Value in Health</i> , 26(9), pp.1353-1362	UK	Cost-effectiveness model	To estimate the health and socioeconomic effects of introducing inclisiran according to a population health agreement in England.	Not PHM – disease management/model development, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Peele et al., (2018). Advancing Value-Based Population Health Management Through Payer–Provider Partnerships: Improving Outcomes for Children With Complex Conditions. <i>The Journal for Healthcare Quality (JHQ)</i> , 40(2), pp.e26-e32	USA	Matched case control	To evaluate whether the intervention affected total cost of care and related cost outcomes for the Medicaid physical health managed care organization; assess whether the initiative maintained or improved quality of care for participants; and conduct a sensitivity analysis to determine what magnitude of savings could be realized under a variety of scenarios.	Not PHM – care improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Percac-Lima et al., (2016). Patient navigation for comprehensive cancer screening in high-risk patients using a population-based health information technology system: a randomized clinical trial. <i>JAMA internal medicine</i> , 176(7), pp.930-937.	USA	RCT	To evaluate patient navigation for breast, cervical, and colorectal cancer screening using a population-based information technology (IT) system within a primary care network.	Not PHM – population-based IT system, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets

Plutzky et al., (2021). Population health management of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol via a remote, algorithmic, navigator-executed program . <i>American Heart Journal</i> , 243, pp.15-27.	USA	Non-RCT	To assess the effectiveness of Population health management of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol via a remote, algorithmic, navigator-executed program.	Not PHM – Population-based EMR screening, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Prendaj et al., (2019). Population management: a tool to improve timely care in pediatric and young adult patients with inflammatory bowel disease . <i>Gastroenterology Research and Practice</i> , 2019(1), p.4702969.	USA	Before and after	To improve timely care in paediatric and young adult patients with inflammatory bowel disease.	Not PHM – Quality improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Radwan et al., (2021). Improving the management of type 2 diabetes through large-scale general practice: the role of a data-driven and technology-enabled education programme . <i>BMJ Open Quality</i> , 10(1)	UK	Before and after	To improve the measurable quality of care in a population where type 2 diabetes care had previously proved challenging.	Not PHM – Quality improvement, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Rubin et al., (2019). Association of a targeted population health management intervention with hospital admissions and bed-days for Medicaid-enrolled children . <i>JAMA Network Open</i> , 2(12), p.e1918306	USA	Quasi experimental study	To estimate the association of a targeted population health management intervention for children eligible for Medicaid with changes in monthly hospital admissions and bed-days.	Not PHM – Quality improvement/ integrated care, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Rust et al., (2011). Economic impact of a Medicaid population health management program . <i>Population Health Management</i> , 14(5), pp.215-222.	USA	A retrospective, nonexperimental study	To analyse claims data from Georgia Medicaid claims files for all program-eligible persons for each relevant time period (intent-to-treat basis).	Not PHM – disease management programme, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets

Schwartz et al., (2010). The impact of an online disease management program on medical costs among health plan members . <i>American journal of health promotion</i> , 25(2), pp.126-133	USA	A retrospective, quasi-experimental, cohort design	To evaluate the economic impact of an online disease management program within a broader population health management strategy.	Not PHM – disease management programme, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Staab et al., (2023). Population health management approach to depression symptom monitoring in primary care via patient portal: a randomized controlled trial . <i>American Journal of Medical Quality</i> , 38(4), pp.188-195	USA	RCT	To evaluate portal-based depression monitoring as an adjunct to usual primary care.	Not PHM – Quality improvement/ integrated care, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Suh et al., (2025). Population health management impact on healthcare utilization and costs in CKD: post-hoc analysis of the kidney CHAMP trial . <i>Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology</i> , pp.10-2215.	USA	Clustered RCT	To conduct a post hoc comparative analysis of the 1-year healthcare utilization between patients who received the PHM intervention compared to usual care with a secondary objective of comparing standardized costs.	Not PHM – disease management, no linked datasets.
Troksa et al., (2020). Effectiveness of a pharmacist-led population health approach to implementing statin therapy in primary prevention patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus . <i>Journal of the American College of Clinical Pharmacy</i> , 3(4), pp.723-728.	USA	Retrospective cohort analysis	To compare statin initiation rates of a pharmacist-led population health initiative in University of Colorado Health System primary care practices.	Not PHM – population health initiative, no multidisciplinary collaboration, no linked datasets
Van beers et al., (2025) Evaluating cloudcare, a population health	The Netherlands	Before and after (observational)	To assess the effect of CloudCare on treatment satisfaction, glycemic control of persons with type1	Not PHM – disease management/service delivery, no multidisciplinary

management system, in persons with type 1 diabetes: an observational study. BMC Endocr Disord:88.Doi: 10.1186/s12902-025-01905-4			diabetes and healthcare professionals' workload and glycemic control of persons with type1 diabetes.	collaboration, no linked datasets
Weltman et al., (2025a). Effect of a population health management intervention on medication therapy problems in people with chronic kidney disease: post hoc analysis of the K-CHAMP cluster-randomized trial. <i>Kidney Medicine</i> , 7(5), p.100995.	USA	Clustered RCT	To characterize medication therapy problems in individuals with nondialysis-dependent chronic kidney disease who participated in the Kidney Coordinated Health Management Partnership (K-CHAMP) trial, which tested a multidisciplinary population health management intervention versus usual care on chronic kidney disease evidence-based care delivery in the primary care setting.	Not PHM – disease management, no linked datasets
Weltmen et al., (2025b). Population health management and guideline-concordant care in CKD: a secondary analysis of Kidney Coordinated HeAlth Management Partnership. <i>Journal of the American Society of Nephrology</i> , 36(5), pp.869-881.	USA	Clustered RCT	To assess the effect of a population health management intervention versus usual care on chronic kidney disease progression and evidence-based care delivery in the primary care setting.	Not PHM – disease management, no linked datasets

9.2 Appendix 2 MEDLINE search strategy

Ovid MEDLINE(R) ALL <1946 to September 26, 2025>

- 1 population health management.ti,ab. 776
- 2 population health management/ 166
- 3 1 or 2 832
- 4 limit 3 to english language 825
- 5 (comment or editorial or letter or "review" or "scoping review" or "systematic review").pt. 6042062
- 6 4 not 5 681

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